

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

DOCTORAL THESIS

**Photoacoustic Analyzer for Natural
Gas and Short-Chain Hydrocarbon
Isotopologues**

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis has been composed by myself.

No portion of this work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or institute of learning.

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Abstract

The objective of this work is the development of a sensor based on photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) which, contrary to the usual field of application of PAS, namely the detection of trace gases, is capable of measuring concentrations of the main alkanes of natural gas as well as of main methane isotopologues.

Knowledge of the natural gas composition, whose main part is methane (75-99% on average), allows a variety of conclusions to be drawn, including its origin and energy content. Furthermore, knowledge of the main methane isotopologues shares of natural gas allows conclusions to be drawn regarding the natural gas maturity and the surrounding rock. The latter can be used to optimize the drilling technology.

Since the absorption spectra of the main alkanes and isotopologues strongly overlap, the determination of the optimal wavelength of the laser source used is not trivial, as far as different molecule types have to be differentiated simultaneously. Therefore, a mathematical algorithm was developed which calculates the optimal wavelength based on the theoretical absorption spectra. The heart of the new sensor is an interband cascade laser (ICL), which emits in the mid-infrared range around $3.3 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength. By applying the injection-current modulation, it is possible to achieve more precise measurement results in comparison to indirect modulation techniques. The behavior of the laser in this mode was initially unknown and has been analyzed in this work with a Michelson interferometer.

Calibration mixtures were produced, using a self-developed gas mixer, whose photoacoustic spectra were calculated by the implemented digital signal processor (DSP) real-time signal processing, based on their photoacoustic signals.

The resulting spectra were used to train the machine-learning algorithm Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), which subsequently determines the concentrations of the main methane isotopologues and the main alkanes, based on their photoacoustic spectra. The evaluation of the developed sensor was carried out on the basis of synthetic gas mixtures, as well as with the help of real natural gas samples from various sources.

It could be shown that PAS is suitable to determine the main methane isotopologues and to analyze natural gas with respect to the composition of its main alkanes. The new sensor determines the composition of the main components of real natural gas samples based on PAS in real time, which enables continuous monitoring of the natural gas composition.

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRDS	Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy
CCD	Charged Coupled Device
DC	Direct Current
DFB-ICL	Distributed-Feedback Interband Cascade Laser
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transformation
DSP	Digital Signal Processor
GC	Gas Chromatography
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IRMS	Isotope Ratio Mass Spectroscopy
LP	Low-Pass
NDIR	Non-Dispersive Infrared
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
PA	Photoacoustic
PAS	Photoacoustic Spectroscopy
PLSR	Partial Least Squares Regression
QCL	Quantum Cascade Laser
QEPAS	Quartz Enhanced Photoacoustic Spectroscopy
QTF	Quartz Tuning Fork
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
TDLS	Tuning Diode Laser Spectroscopy
WMS	Wavelength Modulation Spectroscopy

Chapter 1

Introduction

In 2022, the global primary energy consumption was 160,764 TWh. The energy share of natural gas in primary energy consumption amounted to almost 25% (Our World in Data, 2022). This share indicates how important natural gas still is as an energy source. Natural gas is the result of millions of years of biological processes. The resulting underground energy-rich gas accumulations are the target of the gas extraction industry worldwide. Natural gas consists primarily of short-chain hydrocarbons (Hammer et al., 2003). The exact composition of natural gas provides both natural gas producers and end users a variety of important information. This includes information about the origin of the natural gas and about its energy content (Faramawy et al., 2016). The latter, in particular, is important for both the natural gas producer and the end consumer. Knowledge of the composition allows geological information and also provides information about the deposit itself (Wiersberg and Erzinger, 2007). The energy content provides both billing-relevant information and the basic information for the optimal control of its combustion process (Park et al., 2021; Leicher et al., 2017). Therefore, real-time determination of the composition of the natural gas directly at the consumer would offer significant advantages. These advantages bring economic benefits directly at the customer site in the form of billing according to the energy content actually delivered and the possibility of obtaining highly efficient combustion processes, as the natural gas composition can be continuously monitored.

Gas chromatography (GC) is considered the gold standard for natural gas analysis (Karpash et al., 2010; ISO, 2012). The gas chromatograph offers very accurate results with relative errors smaller than 2%. The dynamic range, with regard to the concentrations of the individual gas components, ranges from ppb (parts per billion) up to 100%. GC requires different operating gases, e.g. helium, synthetic air and hydrogen, depending on the specific configuration of the measurement system. The measurement time is up to 45 minutes depending on the individual setup. In addition, periodic calibration measurements are necessary to maintain the low measurement error (Poole, 2021).

The main component of natural gas, methane, has a significant impact on climate change. While the climate-damaging effect of carbon dioxide (CO_2) is widely known, the up to 34-fold greater negative impact on global warming of methane is for the most part barely known (Jacobson, 2021). The main reason is that the impacts of the individual methane sources on climate change have been insufficiently characterized. The source types, e.g. methane emitted by rice paddies, landfills or cows, are known, but it is hardly possible to quantify the emissions of the single methane sources on a global scale.

Each type of methane source has its individual so-called "methane signature", which results from the ratio of the two main methane isotopologues $^{12}CH_4/^{13}CH_4$. The two main isotopologues have a natural abundance of 98.9% and 1.1%, respectively. Depending on the source type, the ratio known as $\delta^{13}CH_4$ deviates from the standard Pee Dee Belemnite value, allowing conclusions to be drawn about the source (Schwietzke et al., 2016). In order to identify the source, it is therefore necessary to determine the ratio of the main methane isotopologues $^{12}CH_4/^{13}CH_4$ of a sample. Knowing the $\delta^{13}CH_4$ value of the methane in the natural gas reveals more information about the

natural gas itself. Thus, conclusions can be made about its degree of maturity and origin. Valuable geological information can be obtained about the porosity and permeability of the rock containing the natural gas, which can be profitably used to optimize natural gas production (Zhang and Krooss, 2001). Gas chromatography in combination with isotope ratio mass spectroscopy (GC-IRMS) is considered the gold standard for isotopologue analysis (Sessions, 2006). This technology allows to determine the $^{12}\text{CH}_4/^{13}\text{CH}_4$ ratio and thus the $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ value of a sample. This method provides extremely accurate results with errors in the sub-per mil range. However, several calibration measurements with standard samples are necessary during an operating day to maintain accuracy. The complexity of this measurement setup is very high. Laboratory conditions are also essential for accurate and reproducible results. In-situ measurements are therefore impossible.

Another established method of $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ analysis is cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS). This spectroscopic method also provides very precise measurement results with relative measurement errors in the per mil range, but the interfering components of the analyte must be known and their concentrations must not exceed limit values. The measuring time is only a few seconds. While in-situ measurements are possible, the dynamic range in terms of concentration is significantly limited compared to GC-IRMS and is restricted to the ppm range, depending on the instrument. Furthermore, recalibration measurements are required within specified intervals to maintain precision (PICARRO, INC., 2022).

A sensor that can both analyze the major constituents of natural gas hydrocarbons, determine the $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ value of methane and perform these measurements in-situ in real-time, with measurement errors equivalent to GC or even smaller and without cross-sensitivities would be a significant technological advance.

In [Chapter 2](#) the state of the art with regard to known measurement methods for natural gas main alkanes and main isotopologues analysis is described, including photoacoustic spectroscopy.

A laser-based spectroscopic sensor on the basis of photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) could fulfill many of the above-mentioned requirements. PAS is an established method for the identification of trace gases (Palzer, [2020](#)). Radiation emitted by a laser is absorbed by the gas molecules contained in the sample to be analyzed. The energy absorbed by the molecules is converted by relaxation processes, which finally leads to a local temperature increase in the gas (Schilt et al., [2006](#)). This leads to a local pressure change, according to the ideal gas law. The resulting sound wave is detected by a sound detector, e.g. a microphone. The electrical microphone signal allows the quantitative determination of the gas molecules contained in the sample.

In order to accurately determine the concentrations of the individual gas molecules, whose absorption spectra overlap strongly in some cases, a very narrow-band laser radiation source is required, which emits in the mid-infrared range around $3.3 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength. The distributed feedback interband cascade lasers (DFB-ICL) are semiconductor lasers which emit single-mode in the wavelength range in mention with a linewidth of less than 3 MHz (nanoplus, [2023](#)). This enables high-resolution spectroscopy, which allows the differentiation of molecule types whose spectra are strongly overlapping. [Figure 1.1](#) illustrates the strong overlap for the two main methane isotopologues.

FIGURE 1.1: Fundamental vibrational absorption spectra of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ (Gordon et al., 2022).

To enable real-time measurements, the demodulation of the photoacoustic signal is performed using an efficient implementation of the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) on a digital signal processor (DSP) (Elliott, 1987). Since the resulting spectra are highly non-linearly depending on the individual molecule concentrations, the quantitative evaluation can be performed by artificial intelligence (AI). Within the scope of this work, the applicability of the machine-learning based Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) algorithm is demonstrated. PLSR is capable of quantitatively characterizing even complex mixtures with more than two gas components with respect to the individual concentrations (Zifarelli et al., 2020).

PAS has already been successfully applied in its special embodiment as quartz enhanced photoacoustic spectroscopy (QEPAS) with respect to its applicability to artificial natural gas-like samples (Luo et al., 2022). However, no analysis of real natural gas samples, which naturally contain a large number of residual components, was performed.

The sensor to be developed will be validated using artificial samples similar to natural gas generated in the laboratory as well as real natural gas samples. The real natural gas samples originate from various sources. The established GC acts as a reference.

In summary, the PAS-based sensor to be developed should be able to detect both natural gas and main methane isotopologues. The analysis should be carried out in real-time, i.e. the measurement time should only take a few seconds compared to GC, whose analysis time is up to 45 minutes. The compactness of the sensor must allow in-situ measurements.

Project Description and Outline of the Thesis

The main goal of this research project is the development of a PAS-based sensor which allows the detection of the natural gas main components, i.e. methane (CH_4), ethane (C_2H_6) and propane (C_3H_8), and the main methane isotopologues ($^{12}CH_4$ and $^{13}CH_4$).

To achieve this aim, the following subtasks have to be completed:

- Determining the optimal laser wavelength for the methane isotopologues.
- Spectral characterization of injection-current modulated ICL.
- Development of a PA setup for natural gas detection and isotope-selective measurements, including the implementation of the machine learning algorithm Partial Least Squares Regression.
- Calibration of the sensor using synthetic calibration gas mixtures prepared with a gas mixer developed in-house.

- Validation of the sensor by measurements of real natural gas samples using GC reference.

The above mentioned points are corresponding to milestones of this project. Parts of the results have already been published in scientific journals. Within the scope of this work, only the applicability of PAS to in the percentage range concentrated short-chain hydrocarbon samples is demonstrated.

Brief descriptions of the following chapters are given below.

In **Chapter 2**, natural gas is presented with regard to its deposits and the associated production possibilities, its compositions and application. Furthermore, an introduction to the topic of methane and its main isotopologues and their relevance is given. In addition, a description of the established methods of measuring the short-chain main methane isotopologues as well as the main alkanes is given. Moreover, the state of the art of PAS is described with regard to the detection of natural gas and methane isotopologues.

Both the main methane isotopologues and the main alkanes show strongly overlapping absorption spectra regions. For the spectroscopic differentiation of various gas molecules, it is therefore essential to determine an optimal laser wavelength, which allows the analysis of complex gas mixtures with regard to their composition. **Chapter 3** therefore describes a newly developed mathematical algorithm which determines the optimal wavelength for spectroscopy on the basis of the theoretical absorption spectra of the individual gas molecules.

Accurate measurements of the concentrations of the main methane isotopologues and main alkanes require an exact knowledge of the spectral behavior of the ICL operated in the injection-current modulation mode. **Chapter 4** presents a detailed description of a newly developed Michelson interferometer-based method, which allows the determination of the absolute wavelength in direct injection-current modulation mode of the ICL as a function of the laser operating current.

In **Chapter 5** the principle of the photoacoustic effect, which is the basis of PAS, is described in detail. Furthermore, a detailed description of the measurement setup and gas mixer, which was used for the preparation of the calibration gas mixtures, is given. Subsequently, the results obtained with the sensor are presented and discussed in detail. These include measurements of natural gas-like main methane isotopologue mixtures prepared under laboratory conditions.

Chapter 6 presents the advanced PAS measurement setup, which provides DSP-based real-time analysis of gas samples. The calibration of the sensor based on synthetic gas mixtures and subsequently the validation of the sensor based on real natural gas samples is presented. A GC is used as a reference for the measurements.

A summary of the results obtained, as well as an outlook on possible optimizations of the sensor, is presented in **Chapter 7**.

Chapter 2

Natural Gas and Main Methane Isotopologues

The sensor aims to analyze the natural gas in terms of its methane, ethane and propane composition, as well as detect the main methane isotopologue concentrations. To understand the background of the sensor, the natural gas and the main methane isotopologues are described in more detail in the following sections. Their structures, sources, applications and established analysis techniques will be explained.

2.1 Natural Gas

Natural gas consists of 75-99% methane, 1-15% ethane and 1-10% propane, as well as other small amounts of longer-chain hydrocarbons such as butane and pentane, but also of small amounts of nitrogen, carbon dioxide and noble gases (Hammer et al., 2003). As a product of long-term geological formation, created by the decomposition of organic materials such as plants and microorganisms over millions of years, the exact composition of natural gas is highly dependent on its origin (Decourt et al., 2014). Table 2.1 shows the strong location dependence of the methane content.

TABLE 2.1: Natural gas methane share in dependence of its origin (Decourt et al., 2014).

Origin	Country	Methane share
Fayetteville Shale	US	97.3%
Jingbian-Hengshan	China	97.1%
Dovletabad	Turkmenistan	95.2%
Troll Est	Norway	92.8%
Margarita-Huacaya	Bolivia	90.5%
North Dome	Qatar	84.1%
Kangan	Iran	84.1%
Groningen	Netherlands	81.2%
Gorgon	Australia	76.0%
Spleiper	Norway	76.0%
Orenburg	Russia	66.7%
Ghawar	Saudi Arabia	55.6%
Astrakhan	Russia	44.4%
Natuna	Indonesia	26.9%

Natural gas is divided into two groups according to its origin: conventional natural gas and unconventional natural gas. Conventional natural gas is the most common type. It is trapped in cavities in the mantle of the earth and can be extracted by simply drilling from the earth's surface. Unconventional natural gas is trapped in shale rock (shale gas), coal seams (coalbed gas) or sandstone or limestone (tight gas) (Faramawy et al., 2016). Since the rocks in which the unconventional gas is trapped are not sufficiently porous and thus impermeable, fracking technology must be applied. Fracking, the short term for hydraulic fracturing, involves pumping a mixture of water, sand and chemicals under high pressure into the rock, causing cracks to form and releasing the natural gas (Pană et al., 2022).

The crack formation and the subsequent gas release is, to a certain extent, uncontrollable (Meiners et al., 2013). This makes it necessary to identify gas leaks and thus contain potential environmental damage.

As described in [Chapter 1](#), natural gas analysis can be used to carry out a

wide range of optimizations. These include the correct preparation of bills based on the actual energy content delivered to the customer and the increase of the combustion process efficiency.

Natural Gas Analysis Techniques

Gas Chromatography (GC)

Gas chromatography (GC) is considered the gold standard of natural gas analysis. The individual natural gas components are separated in a separation column and then quantitatively detected, for example with a flame ionization detector (FID) (Rhoderick, 2003; Brown et al., 2004). The concentrations of the individual gas components can then be calculated from the recorded chromatogram. The GC functional principle is schematically displayed in **Figure 2.1**.

FIGURE 2.1: Illustration of the functional principle of a gas chromatograph (Dubaj, 2023).

The advantage of GC is the high accuracy and the high dynamic range regarding the concentrations. With a gas chromatograph, measurements with deviations of 1-2% are possible in a dynamic range starting in the ppb range up to 100%. The flame of the FID can be problematic in places with a high risk of explosion, for example at drilling sites. Furthermore, a variety of operating

gases are required, such as helium as carrier gas, synthetic air and hydrogen as combustion gas for the FID. Additionally, the analysis time can be up to 45 minutes depending on the selected analysis parameters. For reliable operation of the gas chromatograph, specially trained personnel is also required, since the operation of the instrument is complex and even small operating errors can completely falsify the measurement (Poole, 2021).

Spectroscopic Methods

Infrared spectroscopy in various forms was tested. The wavelength range was typically 1,000 - 2,000 nm.

A variety of measuring instruments exist which can detect methane, the main component of natural gas, by means of infrared absorption spectroscopy (Compur Monitors, 2021; Mueller-Elektronik AG, 2023). These devices are very compact and thus allow field measurements with very short measuring times. The disadvantage, however, is that they cannot perform a complete natural gas analysis and thus only provide an indication of natural gas leakage. Figure 2.2 illustrates the functional principle of absorption spectroscopy. The radiation emitted by the beam source is absorbed by the analyte. The transmitted part of the radiation is then detected by a detector.

FIGURE 2.2: Illustration of the functional principle of absorption spectroscopy (Jon Chui, 2011).

Non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensors are based on mid-infrared absorption spectroscopy. This technology provides benefits as low cost and sensitivity and allows a miniaturized sensor configuration. Multi-gas detection as simultaneous detection of up to six gases including the natural gas main component methane is possible (Muhiyudin et al., 2020). However, there exists no established natural gas analyzer based on NDIR. The function principle is equivalent to the absorption spectroscopy as displayed in [Figure 2.2](#).

Infrared absorption spectroscopy can also be performed from higher altitudes. Unmanned flying objects (drones) and satellites are used for this purpose (Iwaszenko et al., 2021; Pandey et al., 2023). Their emitted laser radiation is reflected at the earth's surface and thus also allows conclusions to be drawn about the presence of methane in the atmosphere. The advantage of these methods is the large measurement area that can be covered. Since the reflectivity depends on the existing topography of the reflecting point and the interaction path is large due to the measurement height, cross-sensitivities causing larger deviations are to be expected with this measurement method. Fourier transform near-infrared (FTNIR) spectroscopy is an embodiment of infrared spectroscopy (Haghi et al., 2017). Based on a Michelson interferometer, an absorption spectrum is generated in conjunction with the Fourier transform, from which the proportions of the individual components of the gas sample can be determined. The function principle of a Michelson interferometer is displayed in [Figure 2.3](#). The coherent radiation is split by a beam splitter, reflected by both the stationary and moving mirrors and then recombined by the beam splitter. The radiation subsequently coincides with the sample and the transmitted part of the radiation is detected by the detector.

FIGURE 2.3: Illustration of the functional principle of Fourier transform near-infrared (FTNIR) spectroscopy (Sanchonx, 2011).

Another method of infrared spectroscopy is transmission spectroscopy based on hollow-core photonic bandgap fibers (Li et al., 2012). The gas mixture to be analyzed flows into the fiber, where the interaction between the laser radiation and the natural gas occurs. By tuning the laser, an absorption spectrum can be recorded by means of an intensity detector. The resulting spectra can also be used to quantify the individual gas components. An exemplary measurement setup is shown in [Figure 2.4](#).

FIGURE 2.4: Schematic of hollow-core photonic bandgap fiber based measurement setup. SMF stands for single mode fiber, PBGF stands for photonic bandgap fiber and MMF stands for multi mode fiber (© 2012 IEEE, Li et al., 2012).

The advantage of both methods is the comparatively short measurement time in the range of seconds compared to gas chromatography. Water exhibits strong absorption lines in the spectral range mentioned, so that large cross-sensitivities can occur, which leads to considerable measurement deviations. Furthermore, there is a temperature dependency for both methods, which negatively influences the accuracy. Due to the mechanically sensitive structures, vibrations also have a significant negative influence on the measurement results. For these reasons, field measurements are hardly possible.

A further spectroscopy method, which enables the detection of almost all natural gas components, is Raman spectroscopy (Dąbrowski et al., 2019; Kiefer et al., 2008; Petrov et al., 2022). This measurement technique based on the Raman Effect requires laser power in the Watt range, which makes it expensive and eye safety becomes an important issue. Furthermore, a set of calibration measurements are prerequisite to obtain reliable results under a wide range of measurement conditions. Figure 2.5 displays an exemplary measurement setup. The laser beam is reflected by the beam splitter, focussed by the lens and then coincides with the sample. The radiation emitted by the sample is

optically processed by a lens system and guided into the spectrometer, where it is dispersed by the grating. The spectral components are subsequently detected by the charged couple device (CCD) detector.

FIGURE 2.5: Schematic of a Raman spectroscopy setup. CCD stands for charged coupled device (Toommm, 2019).

One of the most recently published spectroscopic technologies for natural gas analysis is based on proton nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy (Duchowny et al., 2022). The advantage of this method is the high accuracy of the results, the relative error is less than 1% in relation to the GC reference. Measurements under different temperature and pressure conditions are also possible. Nevertheless, field measurements are hardly possible since a bench-top NMR, such as the Spinsolve 60 ULTRA NMR spectrometer from Magritek (Aachen, Germany), weighs 60 kg and measures 58 x 43 x 40 cm.

Figure 2.6 displays a schematic of a typical NMR spectrometer. The strength of the static magnetic field in which the sample is located is varied. The

electromagnetic radiation emitted by the sample is detected as a function of the magnetic field strength.

The NMR Spectrometer

FIGURE 2.6: Schematic presentation of a typical nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer (Zia et al., 2019).

Photoacoustic Spectroscopy (PAS)

The first application of the photoacoustic PA effect in spectroscopy was in 1938 by measuring the CO_2 concentration in N_2 . The CO_2 share was approximately 0.2% (Viegerov, 1938).

In 1971, the first measurements of methane in nitrogen were demonstrated, using a chopped helium-neon laser operating in the mid IR ($3.39 \mu\text{m}$) region. The methane detection limit was down to the ppb range (Kreuzer, 1971).

The quantum cascade laser (QCL) presented at Bell Laboratories in 1994 emitted multi-mode radiation at a wavelength of $4.26 \mu\text{m}$ (Faist et al., 1994). QCLs feature continuous tunability next to their compactness and high efficiency. In conjunction with a distributed feedback structure, this laser type emits single-mode. QCLs are commercially available in the wavelength range of

4-14 μm . These properties make them ideal for application in tuning diode laser spectroscopy (TDLS) including PAS.

The interband cascade laser (ICL), invented in 1994 and used experimentally for the first time in 1997, is a radiation source commercially available in the wavelength range of 3-6 μm (Yang, 1995; Lin et al., 1997). This type of laser therefore supplements the spectral range not covered by the QCL. In conjunction with a distributed feedback structure, the ICL emits single-mode with a spectral linewidth of less than 3 MHz (nanoplus, 2023). In combination with its continuous tunability, the ICL reveals the optimal radiation source for the detection of hydrocarbons and especially methane isotopologues.

A further variant of PAS is quartz-enhanced photoacoustic spectroscopy (QEPAS) (Sampaolo et al., 2022). According to the name, the microphone is replaced by a quartz tuning fork (QTF), which typically has a Q-factor greater than 10,000. The first public demonstration of the new technology took place in 2002 (Kosterev et al., 2002). The QTF and thus QEPAS offer some strength and weaknesses as will be explained below.

Because the resonant frequency of the QTF is typically around 32.768 kHz, the associated acoustic resonator lengths must be kept very short. Their typical lengths are in the mm range. If the first longitudinal eigenmode of the resonator is used, the resonator length can be calculated as follows:

$$l = \frac{c}{2f}, \quad (2.1)$$

where l is the length of the resonator, c is the sound velocity of the gas inside the resonator and f equals the modulation frequency (Baumann et al., 2006). This allows a very compact experimental setup. Furthermore, QTFs exhibit quality factors (Q-Factor) around 10,000 in standard atmosphere. Since the Q-Factor is determined as the quotient of center frequency and bandwidth,

the QTF thus acts as a very narrowband bandpass filter, which means that the noise bandwidth is many times smaller compared to measurements with a microphone. This leads to a high SNR (Ma, 2018).

However, the very narrow band filter effect of the QTF can also have a strongly detrimental effect depending on the application. If the modulation frequency of the laser deviates only slightly from the actual resonance frequency of the QTF, the SNR is no longer sufficient to correctly detect concentrations.

Furthermore, the dynamic range of a QEPAS sensor with respect to concentrations is significantly limited compared to the classical PAS sensor. Since the resonant frequency of the resonator used depends on the speed of sound, which is determined by the composition of the analyte, especially in the high concentration range, e.g. for concentrations typical of natural gas, even small deviations from the reference value of the resonator cause a shift in the resonant frequency, which significantly reduces the SNR.

QEPAS has already been successfully used to study the relaxation processes of gas mixtures consisting of methane, ethane and propane, each with fractions in the lower percentage range (Menduni et al., 2022).

First QEPAS measurements involving the simultaneous detection of synthetic natural gas-like mixtures consisting of methane, ethane and propane under laboratory conditions were presented (Luo et al., 2022). The evaluation is based on the signal amplitude at discrete wavelengths. The measurements are so far limited to synthetic mixtures.

2.2 Methane and its Isotopologues

2.2.1 Methane

Methane is the shortest alkane and the natural gas main component, which is composed of one carbon atom and four hydrogen atoms in a tetrahedral structure. The structural formula is shown in [Figure 2.7](#).

FIGURE 2.7: Methane structural formula.

Methane is stored and emitted from a variety of sources around the world. The three largest sources are wetlands, agriculture, and power generation. In total, 570 Mt per year are released into the atmosphere (IEA, 2023). The influence of a chemical compound on global warming, and thus on climate change itself, is described by the Global Warming Potential (GWP). The reference here is the effect of CO_2 , whose GWP is accordingly exactly 1. If we consider an impact period of 100 years, the 100-year GWP of methane is determined to be 34 (Jacobson, 2021). This means that 1 ton of emitted methane in our atmosphere has the same impact as 34 tons of emitted CO_2 , accumulated over a time period of 100 years. Thus, the effect of each unit of emitted methane is many times more harmful to the climate than one unit of emitted CO_2 . [Figure 2.8](#) shows the evolution of the methane content in the atmosphere since 1994, which has risen almost continuously since then. This fact shows the urgency to monitor methane emissions in a targeted systematic way in order to avoid a further continuously rising methane content in our atmosphere. To achieve this goal, it is imperative to identify the sources of methane emission.

FIGURE 2.8: Methane share world trend of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), 1994-2021 (Federal Environment Agency, 2023).

2.2.2 Isotopologues

Two main methane isotopologues exist: $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$. They differ according to their mass number by one neutron in the carbon atom and are structurally identical according to [Figure 2.9](#).

FIGURE 2.9: Structural formulas of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ (left) and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ (right).

The natural abundance of these two molecules are 98.9% and 1.1%, respectively. The isotopologic composition of methane differs depending on the emission source. A sensitive and selective detection of the two main isotologues, $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$, could allow it to determine whether methane traces originate from biogenic or anthropogenic sources (Schwietzke et al., 2016). The fact that anthropogenic sources tend to have slightly higher $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ content can help identify and contain them and, thus, reduce the associated contribution to climate change (Schroll et al., 2020).

In addition to optimizing the drilling technology used to extract natural gas, the application of isotopologic analyses of high methane concentrations can be found in planetary and cometary research. The investigation of the atmospheric composition of planets such as Neptune, Titan and Uranus delivers important information about their formation and evolution (Fletcher et al., 2009; Moses et al., 2020). Astronomic theories, e.g. the core accretion and collapse model (Pollack et al., 1996) which explains the formation scenario of the solar system, could be confirmed in that way.

The isotopologic “signature” of methane, i.e. the concentration ratio of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$, is usually expressed as the deviation from the Pee Dee Belemnite standard in per mil (parts per thousand). This $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ value is defined as:

$$\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4 = \left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{std}}} - 1 \right) \cdot 1000\text{‰} \quad (2.2)$$

where R_{sample} is the $^{12}\text{CH}_4/^{13}\text{CH}_4$ ratio of the sample and $R_{\text{std}} = 0.0112372$ (Reference and intercomparison materials for stable isotopes of light elements. Proceedings of a consultants meeting held in Vienna, 1-3 December 1993, 1995).

Figure 2.10 shows $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ values in per mil for different methane sources. It

can be seen that the range is more than 60 per mil and that the sources can be distinguished with regard to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{H}_4}$ value.

FIGURE 2.10: Isotope-ratios of different methane sources (Schroll et al., 2020, edited).

2.2.3 Analysis Techniques

Gas Chromatography - Isotope Ratio Mass Spectroscopy (GC-IRMS)

A very established and precise method for the analysis of gas mixtures is gas chromatography (GC). This technique allows molecular components to be separated by means of a separation column. The individual molecules are sequentially released from the separation column with a time delay, the so-called retention time, and subsequently detected by a detector, e.g. a flame ionization detector. The resulting chromatogram shows which molecules were present in the sample and their respective concentrations (Poole, 2021). However, since different isotopologues of the same molecule do hardly differ in their retention time, an isotope analysis only by GC is not possible. In order to achieve this, GC is combined with mass spectrometry. The so-called

isotope-ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS) represents the gold standard for isotope analyses.

The main methane isotopologues separated by the gas chromatograph must first be oxidized to CO_2 in the next step. This step converts the isotopologues into molecules with a mass-to-charge ratio of 44 and 45, respectively, which is compatible to the Faraday detector of the isotope-ratio mass spectrometer. The ionized molecules then pass through an upstream magnetic field, which deflects them onto separate paths depending on their specific mass-to-charge ratios. The isotopologue ratio of the original main methane isotopologues can then be measured by the Faraday detector (Sessions, 2006).

In order to achieve exact and reproducible results with a GC-IRMS system, special user know-how and daily reference measurements with reference samples are required to compensate the drift of the system. Due to the complexity of the measurement setup and the high demands on stable ambient conditions, field measurements are hardly possible.

Cavity Ring-down Spectroscopy (CRDS)

As [Figure 1.1](#) shows, the absorption spectra of the two isotopologues are almost identical, due to their congruent chemical structure.

This fact makes spectroscopy-based identification of the two molecules very difficult.

An established spectroscopic method for determining the methane isotopologue composition is cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS). In a resonator, laser radiation is reflected by several mirrors. A part of the radiation is transmitted by the mirrors, as they do not reflect perfectly. The transmitted part is detected by a photodetector, the intensity of which depends on the previous absorption of the gas molecules in the resonator. The photodetector detects an exponentially decreasing intensity. Its decay in connection with the emitted wavelength provides information about the gas composition. To differentiate

the methane isotopologues, tuning of the laser wavelength must be applied. This allows the identification of the $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ shares of the sample to be analyzed, which are the basis for the subsequent $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ calculation. Since the measurement principle is primarily based on the absorption of laser radiation, cross-sensitivities due to the absorption by other molecules are inevitable and lead to erroneous results, even with small concentrations of unknown molecules of the gas matrix. The typical precision of this analysis technique is in the per mil range. Monthly recalibration measurements are required to maintain the specified precision (PICARRO, INC., 2022). In general, field measurements are difficult to realize with this method.

Photoacoustic Spectroscopy (PAS)

An alternative to GC-IRMS and CRDS could be photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) (Palzer, 2020).

PAS is mainly suitable for the detection of trace gases but has been shown to enable the identification and quantification of methane isotopologues in the single-digit per mil range (Giglio et al., 2022) down to the parts per million (ppm) range (Loh and Wolff, 2019/2019b). The latter corresponds to typical concentrations in the atmosphere (van Amstel, 2012; Federal Environment Agency, 2023).

In this work, the applicability of PAS is presented for both the natural gas analysis and isotopologic analysis of highly concentrated methane.

Note: Parts of this **Chapter 2** were published in *Bahr and Wolff, 2022* and *Bahr and Wolff, 2023*.

Chapter 3

Optimal Center Wavelength

Determination for TDLS

Optical spectroscopy is nowadays a well-established method for the analysis of gaseous mixtures. As soon as a high spectral resolution is required, spectrometers usually apply lasers as radiation sources (Demtröder, 2014a; Demtröder, 2014b; Werle et al., 2002). In order to be able to probe different absorption features with a single laser, it is advantageous if its emission wavelength can be varied. Therefore, semiconductor lasers are most appropriate for this task, because they can be spectrally tuned via their operating temperature and current. The tuning range of distributed feedback interband cascade lasers is, for example, of the order of 10 nm at constant laser temperature with an emission linewidth in the single-digit megahertz range (nanoplus, 2023; Zeller et al., 2010; Vurgaftman et al., 2015; Meyer et al., 2020).

When designing a laser spectrometer, the definition of the laser's emission wavelength or, if tunable, its spectral range is crucial for its potential applications. As a matter of course, all the components of interest should exhibit absorption within the range. Furthermore, it is desirable that the absorption strengths of all components are high in order to achieve high detection sensitivity. Simultaneously, interferences of the absorbing compounds should be

excluded to the greatest possible extent in pursuance of avoiding metrological ambiguity and, thus, reach high detection selectivity (Demtröder, 2014a; Demtröder, 2014b).

The identification of the optimal spectral range for a certain application, i.e. for the analysis of a certain mixture of gases, is not trivial. In practice it is usually an educated guess based on the known spectra (Demtröder, 2014b; Dyroff, 2009; Lackner, 2007). The spectra evaluation, i.e. the determination of the concentrations of the individual components, is then typically carried out using a multivariate calibration such as Partial Least Squares Regression. However, the quality of the results, especially the selectivity, strongly depends on the selected wavelength range and the selection becomes increasingly difficult if the single spectra strongly overlap, and even more so if the single components are very similar and their spectra differ only slightly.

The following procedure is customized for lasers of a certain tuning range, such as semiconductor lasers, and delivers its optimal center wavelength. The following section describes the mathematical procedure. After that results regarding the main alkanes and main methane isotopologues are presented.

3.1 Mathematical Procedure

For the application of the method, knowledge of the absorption spectra of all gaseous components in the mixture is required. The spectra can be measured beforehand, i.e. with a Fourier Interferometer, or extracted from databases such as HITRAN, 2024; GEISA, 2022; JPL, 2022 or NIST, 2022. For the calculations in this Chapter 3, only theoretical spectra were used. The flow chart of the method is shown in Figure 3.1. The individual steps are explained in the following subsections.

FIGURE 3.1: Flowchart of the mathematical procedure.

Calculation of Absorption Intensity Differences

In order to measure the individual gas components selectively or with least interference, it is necessary to identify the wavelengths at which the absorption spectra maximally differ from one another (Tomberg et al., 2018). To find these spectral regions, all spectra are normalized to 1. The number of possible combinations of spectra can be calculated using the binomial coefficient. A total number n of gases (spectra) results in:

$$\binom{n}{2} = \frac{n!}{2 \cdot (n-2)!} \quad (3.1)$$

dyads of spectra (Vialar, 2016). The individual absorption intensities of each gas $S(\lambda)$ are then used to calculate the intensity differences $\Delta S_{ij}(\lambda)$ for each pair of gases (i and j) as function of the wavelength λ :

$$\Delta S_{ij}(\lambda) = S_i(\lambda) - S_j(\lambda). \quad (3.2)$$

Application of the Laser Tuning Range

Semiconductor lasers exhibit a limited spectral tuning range. In the case of an interband cascade laser the tuning range $\Delta\lambda$ is typically of the order of 10 nm (nanoplus, 2023; Zeller et al., 2010; Zeller et al., 2010; Vurgafman et al., 2015; Meyer et al., 2020). This has to be considered for the determination of best suited spectral range. The influence is represented by a sliding integral

(Q-function) of the individual differences:

$$Q_{ij}(\lambda) = \int_{\lambda - \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}}^{\lambda + \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}} |\Delta S_{ij}(\lambda')| d\lambda' \quad (3.3)$$

Q_{ij} represents a measure of the spectral deviation of the species i and j in the wavelength range from $(\lambda - \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2})$ to $(\lambda + \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2})$. Due to the dependence of the integral limits on the wavelength, the integral acts like a window function. This window is sliding over the entire spectral range. Thus, the integral can also be described as a sliding integral.

Differences $\Delta S_{ij}(\lambda)$ of components with weak absorption can lead to inaccurate results in the following steps and, therefore, need to be suppressed. In order to do this, an auxiliary value D_{ij} is defined:

$$D_{ij} = \int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_1} |\Delta S_{ij}(\lambda)| d\lambda. \quad (3.4)$$

Here, λ_1 and λ_0 are the lower and the upper boundary of the wavelength range under evaluation. Subsequently, a parameter $0 < p \ll 1$ has to be determined empirically, which is related to the threshold values Q_{thij} of the individual Q-functions:

$$Q_{thij} = p \cdot D_{ij}. \quad (3.5)$$

The threshold values Q_{thij} are needed to obtain an unambiguous result for the optimal laser wavelength. The parameter p is chosen optimally if Equation (3.9) provides only a single range – the absolute maximum. Due to the complexity of the D_{ij} values, the optimum parameter p can only be selected

empirically. Q_{thij} is applied to $Q_{ij}(\lambda)$ according to:

$$\tilde{Q}_{ij}(\lambda) = \begin{cases} Q_{ij}(\lambda), & \text{if } Q_{ij}(\lambda) > Q_{thij} \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

In a next step the filtered Q-functions $\tilde{Q}_{ij}(\lambda)$ are multiplied by the difference spectra:

$$\Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda) = \Delta S_{ij}(\lambda) \cdot \tilde{Q}_{ij}(\lambda). \quad (3.7)$$

$\Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda)$ can be considered to be the difference spectrum for the gas pair i and j filtered by the Q-functions.

Combining the Results of all Component Pairs

The “filtered” difference $\Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda)$ is large for wavelength regions, in which the spectra of a certain gas pair differs and, at the same time, absorption is strong. In order to consider the contribution of all possible gas pairs, all filtered differences are multiplied:

$$P(\lambda) = \prod_{i,j=1}^n \Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda), \text{ where } i < j. \quad (3.8)$$

The product $P(\lambda)$ is large if the previous conditions are satisfied for all gas component dyads. For absorption-weak wavelengths or wavelengths at which the spectra of the species do not differ significantly, the product $P(\lambda)$ is small. Thus, wavelength ranges with large values of $P(\lambda)$ mark the regions preferable for a sensitive and selective measurement. In order to consider the limited tuning range of semiconductor lasers an integral parameter equivalent to

Equation (3.3) is introduced:

$$P_{int}(\lambda) = \int_{\lambda - \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}}^{\lambda + \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}} |P(\lambda')| d\lambda'. \quad (3.9)$$

Center Wavelength Determination

The wavelength region around the maximum of $P_{int}(\lambda)$ indicates the spectral range in which the center wavelength of the semiconductor laser should ideally be located. The median of P_{int} is chosen as center wavelength since it considers all values of P_{int} and is therefore “well-balanced”.

In general, the median m of a function $f(x)$ is defined as (Georgii, 2015):

$$\int_{-\infty}^m f(x) dx = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x) dx. \quad (3.10)$$

The application of this definition leads to the optimal center wavelength λ_c of the laser:

$$\int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_c} P_{int}(\lambda) d\lambda = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_1} P_{int}(\lambda) d\lambda. \quad (3.11)$$

In the intervals $-\infty$ to λ_0 and λ_1 to $+\infty$, the function values of $P_{int}(\lambda)$ are zero. For this reason, the integration limits in Equation (3.11) can be changed from $-\infty$ to λ_0 and from $+\infty$ to λ_1 .

With the aid of software like MATLAB, 2022 it is easy to extract λ_c from this equation.

3.2 Exemplary Results

The mathematical procedure described above was programmed in MATLAB and applied to assumptive gas mixtures. The absorption spectra of the single components were measured beforehand or extracted from the HITRAN database, respectively (Loh and Wolff, 2017; Loh and Wolff, 2019a; HITRAN, 2024).

The algorithm was tested on combinations of gaseous, i.e. short-chained, hydrocarbons. Their strongest absorption is associated with the fundamental vibrations and occurs in the mid-infrared wavelength region, typically between 3 and 4 μm (Alrefae et al., 2014). The lower and the upper boundary of the wavelength range under evaluation (λ_0 and λ_1) are 3000 nm and 3600 nm, respectively. Since the absorption spectra strongly overlap, it is often not possible to visually identify the optimal spectral range for the analysis.

3.2.1 Mixture of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$

In a first test, a mixture of the two main isotopologues of methane, $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$, has been investigated. Figure 3.2 shows both absorption spectra normalized to one. The graph of the $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ isotopologue does not reach intensity “one” because downsampling had to be performed after normalization so that the described computational operations can be applied to both isotopologues.

FIGURE 3.2: Absorption spectra of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$, based on HITRAN, 2024.

The two gases were selected because the spectral positions of the single rotational lines in the respective P- and R-branch are almost identical, but the positions of the Q-branches clearly differ. The $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ Q-branch is approximately located between 3310 and 3320 nm; the $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ one between 3320 and 3330 nm. Since the Q-branches additionally exhibit relatively high absorption strength, it would be expected that the laser of a perfectly suited spectrometer (tunability: 10 nm) covers a large part of these regions.

Because this mixture contains only two gases, the measure of the spectral deviation filtered with the Q-function, $\Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda)$, equals the product parameter $P(\lambda)$ according to Equation (3.8) which is displayed in Figure 3.3. $P_{int}(\lambda)$, the integral of $P(\lambda)$ over the 10 nm laser tuning range according to Equation (3.9), is shown as well.

FIGURE 3.3: Evaluation of the mixture $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$, all quantities are normalized to “one”.

Figure 3.3 shows $P_{int}(\lambda)$ for $p = 8.5\%$ on the larger scale whereas the dark grey vertical line represents its median which corresponds to the optimal center wavelength of the laser according to Equation (3.11). The laser exhibits a center wavelength of 3320.7 nm and reaches from 3315.7 to 3325.7 nm. Since this covers a large part of the Q-branches of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ as it would have been expected, the test represents an evidentiary confirmation of the mathematical procedure.

The parameter p according to Equation (3.5) determines the quality of the result to a large extent. Figure 3.4 shows $P_{int}(\lambda)$ around its absolute maxima at 3315 and 3326 nm for values of p between 1 and 9%. The individual curves are shifted by 0.5 relative to each other in vertical direction so that the progress can be clearly seen. With increasing p the secondary maxima between 3200 and 3300 nm and between 3350 and 3450 nm successively disappear whereas the

main maximum remains almost unaffected. From 8.5% on only the absolute maximum remains, and for that reason this value was chosen in the previous paragraph.

FIGURE 3.4: Normalized $P_{int}(\lambda)$ of the mixture $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ for different values of p .

3.2.2 Mixture of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$, $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6$ and $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$

The second test of the algorithm was performed on a (simulative) mixture of methane, ethane and ethylene (all carbon atoms with the mass number 12). [Figure 3.5](#) displays the three absorption spectra normalized to one. This combination was chosen, because it is apparently not possible to visually identify the most suited wavelength range for a spectroscopic analysis with a single laser (tunability 10 nm).

The purpose of [Figure 3.6](#) is the visualization of the intermediate results. It shows:

- The $\Delta S_{ij,Q}(\lambda)$ according to Equation (3.7) for the three possible gas dyads $^{12}\text{CH}_4 - ^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6$, $^{12}\text{CH}_4 - ^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ and $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6 - ^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$.
- $P(\lambda)$ (the product of all filtered differences according to Equation (3.8)) and
- $P_{int}(\lambda)$ (the integral of $P(\lambda)$ over the 10 nm laser tuning range according to Equation (3.9)).

Figure 3.6 is used exclusively to visualise the intermediate results.

FIGURE 3.5: Absorption spectra of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$, $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6$ and $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$, based on Loh and Wolff, 2017, Loh and Wolff, 2019a and HITRAN, 2024.

FIGURE 3.6: Evaluation of the mixture $^{12}\text{CH}_4$, $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6$ and $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$, all quantities are normalized to "one".

The resulting optimal center wavelength of the laser according to Equation (3.11) equals 3347.3 nm. It is marked in Figure 3.6 with a dark grey vertical line. The laser allows spectral tuning from 3342.3 to 3352.3 nm. It covers the characteristically high $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ line at ca. 3346 nm as well as the two strongest rotational lines of $^{12}\text{C}_2\text{H}_6$ and one relatively strong and discrete line of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$. The range is marked in Figure 3.5 (yellow box). The result of this evaluation is very plausible and represents another confirmation for the applicability of the mathematical procedure.

3.3 Conclusion

The method is particularly suitable for spectrometers based on tunable diode lasers. A prerequisite for its application is that absorption spectra of all gases in the mixture are known. The mathematical procedure identifies wavelength regions, in which the spectra of the single gases significantly differ and, at the

same time, the absorption is strong. The definition of a threshold ensures that the best suited spectral region is found. The median of the optimal spectral range is selected as the laser's center wavelength.

The procedure was tried on two simulative gas mixtures. A first test was carried out on a mixture that allowed it to identify the perfect region through educated guessing. That the algorithm yielded the expected region is a convincing confirmation of the method. The second test of the algorithm was performed on a mixture where it was obviously not possible to visually identify the most suited wavelength range. The result of this evaluation is very plausible and represents another confirmation for the method. Finally, it should be mentioned that the applicability depends primarily on the available spectra and that the number of components in the mixture is theoretically limited only by the available computing power. In practice, a spectrometer based on a single diode laser will probably never be applied to mixtures of more than 10 gases.

A limitation of the practical applicability is the fact that the algorithm is based on perfect spectra. Noise and other aspects of metrological reality are not taken into account. Only under these conditions are the results independent of the concentration of the individual components and their ratios.

Note: This [Chapter 3](#) was published in *Bahr et al., 2022*.

Chapter 4

Spectral Characterization of Modulated ICLs

The exact knowledge of the emission wavelength is one of the fundamental parameters in laser spectroscopy. Several spectroscopic techniques such as photoacoustics require a modulation of the radiation as a matter of principle (Besson et al., 2004).

Semiconductor lasers can easily be modulated by variation of the operating current. In doing so amplitude as well as wavelength modulation are possible. However, assuming a simple, frequency-independent proportionality between wavelength and current, as it is observable in continuous wave (cw) operation, can lead to significant measurement errors (Demtröder, 2014a). The determination of the momentary wavelength becomes extraordinarily difficult if the semiconductor laser emitting in the mid-infrared (e.g., an interband cascade laser or ICL) is modulated with a higher frequency.

At present, different methods and measuring devices exist that enable the spectral characterization of semiconductor lasers such as ICLs (Meyer et al., 2020). However, all of them are primarily applicable for cw radiation. Often, prism or grating spectrometers are used as measuring instruments, which are based on diffraction and interference phenomena, respectively. A further method is the Fourier transform interferometer (FTIR), which is based on a Michelson interferometer and determines the emission spectrum by Fourier

transform of the interferogram (Smith, 2011).

Another possibility is the “wavemeter” of BRISTOL Instruments, Inc. (Victor, New York, NY, USA). It measures the wavelength of a laser on the basis of a Michelson interferometer, provides accuracy in the ppm range and represents the state of the art for wavelength measurements in continuous wave operation (Bristol, 2020; Bristol, 2023; Veracious Statistics Research, 2021).

If the laser is operated in current-modulation mode, there are only few possibilities. One approach determines the wavelength change as a function of the laser operating current ($d\lambda/dI$) (Du et al., 2016). The experimental setup is based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer and the change in wavelength is calculated using a mathematical algorithm which is not further described. This method does not allow a determination of the absolute wavelength as a function of the current. Another possibility for a fast wavelength measurement is a heterodyne (or super-heterodyne) Michelson interferometer. It differs from the homodyne interferometer in that a beat signal is analyzed that results from the superposition of the radiation to be analyzed and that of a second laser. This technique is particularly well suited if the phase of the beat signal is required (Schuldt et al., 2017; Yoon et al., 2009; Dändliker et al., 1988).

A US patent from 2019 represents the latest research progress regarding the determination of the absolute wavelength of current-modulated semiconductor lasers. It is pointed out that, on the basis of an interferometer, the absolute wavelength of tunable lasers can be determined very precisely. The rudimentarily described method mentions the need for a reference wavelength, e.g., a gas absorption line (R. Seeley, 2019).

To the best of my knowledge there is only one commercially available device for the determination of mid-infrared wavelengths in modulation mode. The “NLIR 2.0–5.0 μm spectrometer” of NLIR ApS (Farum, Denmark) is based on non-linear optics and transforms the laser radiation into the near-infrared range, which is subsequent analyzed using a diffraction grating and a CMOS

sensor (NLIR, 2022). According to the manufacturer the maximum sampling rate of the instrument is 130 kHz. The spectral resolution of the NLIR is around 1.5 nm.

Due to the fact that the currently available methods for the spectral characterization of current-modulated semiconductor lasers, especially DFB interband cascade lasers, are not sufficient to achieve a high spectral resolution, new techniques are required.

4.1 Methods and Materials

In the following, two methods for determining the absolute wavelength of modulated semiconductor lasers, in this case interband cascade lasers, are described. Both are based on the same experimental setup and exhibit advantages and disadvantages due to the different signal processing.

4.1.1 Experimental Setup

Figure 4.1 shows the schematic experimental setup for measuring the laser wavelength as function of the current during modulation. It is based on a homodyne Michelson interferometer with silver mirrors and a CaF₂ beam splitter (Steel, 1983). The difference between the two distances a and b is of great importance, because it determines the quality of the results. If a and b approach each other, the number of maxima and minima in the interference signal decreases, which is disadvantageous for the spectral characterization. Simultaneously, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) increases due to the decreasing distance to the detector. This has a positive effect on the evaluation. If one of the two paths becomes significantly larger than the other, the number of maxima and minima increases, however, the SNR decreases due to the longer distance to the detector. In order to achieve a good compromise between spectral resolution and SNR, the distances have to be empirically optimized.

FIGURE 4.1: Experimental setup based on a Michelson interferometer.

The Thorlabs PDA07P2 employs an InAsSb detector and provides a bandwidth of 9 MHz. The ICL 1541, manufactured by nanoplus GmbH (Gerbrunn, Germany), was characterized with an average wavelength λ_0 of 3333 nm and a spectral linewidth of less than 3 MHz. The laser can be operated at temperatures between 15 and 27 degrees Celsius. The Peltier element used to regulate the temperature of the laser chip is optimally integrated into the laser housing by the laser manufacturer nanoplus GmbH and enables optimum laser temperature regulation. Stimulated emission occurs with operating currents between 25 and 45 mA. The average optical output power is 5.5 mW. During cw operation it can be assumed that the wavelength is proportional to the current with $d\lambda/dI = 0.16$ nm/mA. The ICL is driven by the Thorlabs TLD001 diode driver and its temperature is controlled by the Thorlabs temperature controller TTC001. The laser diode current can be accurately set to 10 μ A with a noise level < 3 μ A rms. The ICL chip is installed in a TO66 housing including a Peltier element for temperature regulation and the temperature sensor. Within the scope of the technical possibilities, the laser wavelength is optimally stabilized. An Agilent 33220A function generator (Agilent, Santa

Clara, CA, USA) is used to modulate the operating current of the diode driver. The intensity detected by the detector is converted into a voltage signal which is sampled by a PicoScope 5444D (Pico Technology, Cambridgeshire, UK) with 16 bit resolution. The sampling rate is 62.5 MS/s. The sampled signal is then subjected to processing by means of MATLAB. After the signal is time sliced, Savitzky-Golay based filtering of the signal is performed to eliminate high frequency noise (Press and Teukolsky, 1990). This optimizes the precision of the subsequent detection of the local maxima and minima in the interference signal. Subsequently, different mathematical equations and methods are applied according to the procedures described in Sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3, respectively.

4.1.2 Non-Linear Regression

Spectral Characterization

The electric field (E-field) component of the ICL radiation at the location of the detector can be described as (Peatross and Ware, 2015):

$$E(t) = \hat{E}(t) \cdot e^{j(\omega t + \varphi_0)} \quad (4.1)$$

where ω is the instantaneous angular frequency of the E-field and φ_0 is the initial phase of the laser radiation. The stochastic phase noise of the laser radiation is neglected here, since it would only increase the complexity of the equation and does not add any value to the following calculations. $\hat{E}(t)$ corresponds to the amplitude and is time-dependent because the ICL is modulated. One part of the laser beam is transmitted through the beam splitter and reflected by mirror (1). When it hits the detector, its E-Field equals:

$$E_1(t) = \hat{E}(t) \cdot e^{j(\omega t + \varphi_0)}. \quad (4.2)$$

The second part of the laser beam is reflected at the beam splitter, then reflected at mirror (2) and subsequently transmitted through the beam splitter. Due to the path difference $s_d = 2(b - a)$, it hits the detector delayed by a time t_d compared to $E_1(t)$:

$$t_d = \frac{2(b - a)}{c} = \frac{s_d}{c}, \quad (4.3)$$

where c corresponds to the speed of light. If this part of the laser beam hits the detector, the E-field component can be described with:

$$E_2(t) = E_1(t - t_d) = \hat{E}(t - t_d) \cdot e^{j\omega \cdot (t - t_d) + \varphi_0}. \quad (4.4)$$

If the laser current is modulated, the wavelength (angular frequency ω) changes continuously as a function of time. This results in the following relationships for the E-field components hitting the detector:

$$E_1(t) = \hat{E}(t) \cdot e^{j\left(\int_0^t \omega(\tau) d\tau + \varphi_0\right)}, \quad (4.5)$$

$$E_2(t) = \hat{E}(t - t_d) \cdot e^{j\left(\int_0^{t-t_d} \omega(\tau) d\tau + \varphi_0\right)}. \quad (4.6)$$

The integration of the angular frequency becomes necessary because it is not constant over time anymore.

If both partial beams hit the detector, the sum of both components equals:

$$E_s(t) = E_1(t) + E_2(t). \quad (4.7)$$

Since the detector only detects intensities, the relationship between the E-field components and the intensity must be applied (Kull, 2010):

$$I(t) \propto |E_s(t)|^2. \quad (4.8)$$

Since the absolute value of the intensity is of no importance for the further considerations, the following results for the detector signal:

$$I(t) \propto \hat{E}^2(t) + \hat{E}^2(t - t_d) + 2\hat{E}(t) \cdot \hat{E}(t - t_d) \cdot \cos\left(\int_{t-t_d}^t \omega(\tau) d\tau\right) \quad (4.9)$$

Due to the extremely short interferometer delay time ($t_d < 1 \text{ ns}$), it can be assumed that $E(t) \approx E(t - t_d)$, which simplifies Equation (4.9) to:

$$I(t) \propto 2\hat{E}^2(t) + 2\hat{E}^2(t) \cdot \cos\left(\int_{t-t_d}^t \omega(\tau) d\tau\right) \quad (4.10)$$

Therefore, the detector signal depends particularly on the interferometer delay time and corresponds theoretically to an oscillation between $4\hat{E}^2(t)$ and zero. The instantaneous angular frequency of the laser $\omega(t)$ can be derived from the phase $\varphi(t)$ of the detector signal. This is possible due to the elementary relationship between the angular frequency and the phase $\omega(t) = \frac{d\varphi(t)}{dt}$ (Giancoli, 2023):

$$\omega_{If}(t) = \dot{\varphi}(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\int_{t-t_d}^t \omega(\tau) d\tau \right), \quad (4.11)$$

where $\omega_{If}(t)$ corresponds to the angular frequency of the interferometer signal. Since the integration interval in Equation (4.11) corresponds to the delay time t_d , the infinitesimal value $\omega(\tau)$ can be considered approximately constant in the interval. Thus Equation (4.11) results in:

$$\omega_{If}(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \omega(t) \cdot t_d = 2\pi \cdot c \cdot t_d \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \frac{1}{\lambda(t)} = -\frac{2\pi \cdot c \cdot t_d}{\lambda^2(t)} \cdot \frac{d\lambda(t)}{dt}. \quad (4.12)$$

The square of the wavelength $\lambda^2(t)$ can be approximated by the square of the average wavelength λ_0^2 given in the data sheet of the respective semiconductor laser. Understandably, this does not apply to $\lambda(t)$ in the derivative. Resolved according to the wavelength change as function of time and with

the relationship $s_d = c \cdot t_d$ according to Equation (4.3), it follows that:

$$\frac{d\lambda(t)}{dt} = -\frac{f_{If}(t) \cdot \lambda_0^2}{c \cdot t_d} = -\frac{f_{If}(t) \cdot \lambda_0^2}{s_d}, \quad (4.13)$$

with the momentary frequency of the interference $f_{If}(t)$. The negative sign on the right side has no meaning for further calculations. Due to the symmetry of the cosine function, it is not possible to distinguish between positive and negative phases of the interferometer signal. The negative sign can therefore be omitted.

However, the wavelength change as function of the change in current is sought. The modulation of the current is, in this case, sawtooth-shaped with the rate of change k (unit: $\frac{\text{mA}}{\text{s}}$):

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = k \quad (4.14)$$

Equation (4.14) solved for dt and inserted into Equation (4.13) delivers (if the sign is omitted):

$$\frac{d\lambda(I)}{dI} = \frac{f_{If}(I) \cdot \lambda_0^2}{s_d \cdot k}. \quad (4.15)$$

The wavelength as a function of the operating current can be determined from the differential quotient by means of integration if an absolute wavelength is known as reference point:

$$\lambda(I_1) = \int_{I_0}^{I_1} \frac{d\lambda(I)}{dI} dI + \lambda(I_0). \quad (4.16)$$

The reference wavelength $\lambda(I_0)$ can, for instance, be determined experimentally. If the modulated laser beam passes a cell filled with a gas that shows a strong and distinct absorption line in the expected wavelength range, the

transmission of the interference signal provides the reference wavelength (Stewart, 2021).

Error Estimation

The wavelength as function of current calculated according to Equation (4.16) is subject to deviations due to measurement errors and approximations.

Equation (4.15) inserted into Equation (4.16) results in:

$$\lambda(I_1) = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{s_d \cdot k} \int_{I_0}^{I_1} f(I) dI + \lambda(I_0). \quad (4.17)$$

The coefficients of the regression function $f(I)$ can be determined applying a polynomial regression of second (or larger) degree using the evaluated frequency values of the interference signal. As the degree of the polynomial increases, the residuals will initially decrease and then converge. However, the computational effort increases continuously. After integration, a closed analytical expression is obtained, depending on metrologically determined quantities, which are subject to error tolerances. The maximum possible error can then be calculated by the sum of the following components:

$$\Delta\lambda(I_1)_{\lambda_0} = \frac{2\lambda_0}{s_d \cdot k} \left(\frac{a_1}{3} I_1^3 + \frac{a_2}{2} \cdot I_1^2 + a_3 I_1 - \frac{a_1}{3} I_0^3 - \frac{a_2}{2} \cdot I_0^2 - a_3 I_0 \right) \cdot \Delta\lambda_0, \quad (4.18)$$

$$\Delta\lambda(I_1)_{s_d} = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{s_d^2 \cdot k} \left(\frac{a_1}{3} I_1^3 + \frac{a_2}{2} \cdot I_1^2 + a_3 I_1 - \frac{a_1}{3} I_0^3 - \frac{a_2}{2} \cdot I_0^2 - a_3 I_0 \right) \cdot \Delta s_d \text{ and} \quad (4.19)$$

$$\Delta\lambda(I_1)_{\lambda(I_0)} = \Delta\lambda(I_0), \quad (4.20)$$

where $a_{1...3}$ stand for the coefficients of the regression function and $\Delta\lambda_0$, Δs_d and $\Delta\lambda(I_0)$ for the absolute errors of the individual variables. The influence

of the integration according to Equation (4.17) on the maximum error can be estimated by the Riemann sum (McGregor et al., 2011). It includes the standard deviation of the instantaneous frequency $f(I)$, which results from the non-linear regression.

An additional error is caused by approximations. One of the effects is the standard deviation σ_{I_f} of the interference signal which describes the distribution of the instantaneous frequencies around the regression function. For its share of the maximum wavelength error $\Delta\lambda_{\sigma_{I_f}}$ applies:

$$\Delta\lambda_{\sigma_{I_f}} = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{s_d \cdot k} \cdot \pm\sigma_{I_f} \cdot (I_1 - I_0). \quad (4.21)$$

The result must be added to that from Equations (4.18) to (4.20).

4.1.3 Direct Evaluation of Fringes

Spectral Characterization

The equations presented in Section 4.1.2 are also valid for the method labeled “direct evaluation of fringes”. The cosine occurring in the interference signal, according to Equation (4.10), corresponds to local maxima and minima, hereafter referred to as fringes, due to constructive and destructive interference. The conditions for constructive and destructive interference depend mainly on the path difference of the Michelson interferometer whereas:

$$s_d = n \cdot \lambda \quad \text{and} \quad (4.22)$$

$$s_d = (2n + 1) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2}, \quad (4.23)$$

respectively, with $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (Brodie and Booth, 2010). By means of a reference wavelength based on an absorption line in the transmission spectrum, the absolute wavelengths of the individual fringes according to Equations (4.22)

and (4.23) can be calculated: After n of the local extremum nearest to the reference wavelength has been determined, all other extrema can be assigned by iterating n . Subsequently, the wavelengths in between the individual extreme points are calculated by non-linear regression. Therefore, the method “direct evaluation of fringes” combines established physical and mathematical procedures.

Error Estimation

The accuracy of the results of this method depends, besides the exactness of the reference wavelength, mainly on the accuracy of the path difference s_d . Its influence on the maximum error of the frequency of fringes f_f results in:

$$\Delta f_f = n \cdot \frac{c}{s_d^2} \cdot \Delta s_d \quad \text{and} \quad (4.24)$$

$$\Delta f_f = \frac{2n+1}{2} \cdot \frac{c}{s_d^2} \cdot \Delta s_d, \quad (4.25)$$

for constructive and destructive interference, respectively, where Δs_d corresponds to the maximum error of s_d and the natural number n to the number of fringes which lie to the left or right of the reference wavelength. Due to the linear relationship between Δf_f and n , it is advantageous to base the calculation on the frequency and convert it subsequently to wavelength.

4.2 Results

The two methods were tested using the nanoplus ICL 1541. For the test a sawtooth modulation between 25 and 45 mA was applied. The duty cycle of the sawtooth signal was 100%. Measurements were conducted at 15, 21 and 27 degrees Celsius in order to cover the entire dynamic range. The gas used for the determination of the reference wavelength is ethane with a purity of 99.999% and 99% nitrogen content. Measurements were taken at a gas

temperature of approximately 22 degrees Celsius and a pressure of 1000 mbar.

Figures 4.2 to 4.6 show exemplary results obtained by the two methods.

FIGURE 4.2: Exemplary interference signal at 100 Hz modulation frequency and 15 degrees Celsius laser temperature.

FIGURE 4.3: Change of wavelength as function of operating current for different modulation frequencies based on the non-linear regression method at 15 degrees Celsius laser temperature.

FIGURE 4.4: Absolute wavelength as function of operating current for different modulation frequencies based on the non-linear regression method at 15 degrees Celsius laser temperature.

FIGURE 4.5: Absolute wavelength as function of the operating current for three different laser temperatures based on the non-linear regression method at 100 Hz modulation frequency.

FIGURE 4.6: Absolute wavelength as function of the operating current for three different laser temperatures based on the direct evaluation of fringes at 100 Hz modulation frequency; the crosses mark the calculation points.

The measuring ranges of the two methods differ, because discontinuities in the interference signal are bridged in the non-linear regression method. They can be extracted directly from [Figures 4.5](#) and [4.6](#), respectively. [Table 4.1](#) lists the measuring ranges as well as the wavelength errors according to [Equation \(4.18\)](#) - [Equation \(4.21\)](#).

TABLE 4.1: Natural gas methane share in dependence of its origin.

Method	Measuring Range	Wavelength Error
Non-linear Regression method	30-45 mA	$\Delta\lambda = \pm 0.12$ nm
Direct evaluation of fringes	31-45 mA	$\Delta\lambda = \pm 0.030$ nm

[Table 4.2](#) presents the spectral range of the ICL as function of the modulation frequency.

TABLE 4.2: Spectral range of nanoplus ICL 1541.

Modulation Frequency (kHz)	Wavelength Range (nm)	$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	$\Delta\lambda$ (Relative to cw)
cw	3327.52–3330.57	3.05	1.00
0.1	3328.48–3330.27	1.79	0.59
0.4	3328.55–3330.01	1.46	0.48
1	3328.60–3329.95	1.35	0.44
3	3328.67–3329.84	1.17	0.38
6	3328.73–3329.74	1.01	0.33
12	3328.80–3329.63	0.83	0.27
20	3328.87–3329.53	0.66	0.22
30	3328.88–3329.42	0.54	0.18

Figure 4.7 shows the spectral dynamic range $\Delta\lambda$ (relative to cw) as a function of frequency on the basis of the values in Table 4.2. According to the shape of the graph in Figure 4.7, it is reasonable to assume that the relationship shown corresponds to the natural logarithm.

FIGURE 4.7: Spectral dynamic range $\Delta\lambda$ (relative to cw) as function of modulation frequency.

4.3 Discussion

Due to the lack of spectrometric tools, the spectral performance of mid-infrared semiconductor lasers under modulation has not yet been systematically investigated. The fact that the spectral dynamic range (i.e., the spectral modulation depth) decreases with increasing modulation frequency, as shown in Table 4.2 and Figure 4.7, was new even to the laser manufacturer. There is also no theoretical approach with which these measurement results could be

compared.

However, the emission wavelength of a semiconductor laser is primarily determined by the geometric dimensions and the refractive index of the semiconductor material, and both parameters are significantly influenced by the laser temperature and thus indirectly by the injection current. The temperature tuning factor for the ICL 1541 used in this investigation is 0.35 nm/K. A plausible explanation could therefore be a frequency-dependent temperature distribution of the semiconductor laser material. As the modulation frequency increases, there is less time available for establishing a thermal equilibrium. A changing frequency would therefore lead to a changing temperature distribution or the occurrence of (additional) inhomogeneities. Effects on the spectral emission are to be expected (Zeller et al., 2010).

Figure 4.2 does not perfectly correspond to the mathematical description given by Equation (4.10). From the equation it would be expected that mutual cancellation of the DC and AC components and adding occur alternately. However, this is not observable because on the one hand Equation (4.10) is based on several approximations and on the other hand the alignment of the individual partial beams in the Michelson interferometer is not perfect. The approximations include the proportional relationship of the intensity and the neglect of the delay time t_d .

An analysis of the results presented in Figures 4.5 and 4.6 shows that the wavelength difference between the two methods is only of the order of a few hundredths of a nanometer. Figures 4.3 and 4.4 demonstrate that, with increasing modulation frequency, the wavelength change as function of operating current decreases. This limits the spectral range of the ICL which is particularly relevant for wavelength modulation.

The spectral tuning characteristics of the modulated laser $d\lambda/dI$ (Figure 4.3) and $\lambda(I)$ (Figures 4.4 to 4.6) can be approximated by quadratic polynomials and cubic polynomials, respectively. Compared to cw operation, the ICL thus shows a clearly nonlinear spectral behavior.

In cw operation, the tuning coefficient $d\lambda/dI$ for the nanoplas ICL 1541 equals approximately 0.16 nm/mA. Figure 4.3 shows that with decreasing modulation frequencies the individual curves approach this constant value.

A direct comparison of the methods in Section 4.1 shows that the direct evaluation of fringes requires fewer physical quantities for the calculation of the absolute wavelength and less computational effort compared to the non-linear regression method. This results in an overall higher precision.

The “non-linear regression method” on the other hand enables a compensation of discontinuities in the interference signal and, therefore, a larger measuring range compared to the direct evaluation of the fringes.

The direct evaluation of fringes is a factor of four more precise than the non-linear regression method, as fewer error-prone variables are included. However, the accuracy of both methods strongly depends on the precision of the reference wavelength derived from the transmission spectrum. An advantage of the non-linear regression method over the direct evaluation of fringes is a larger measurement range.

Compared to the state of art, both methods achieve a significantly higher resolution, which does additionally have the potential to be optimized by adjusting the path length difference of the Michelson interferometer.

A heterodyne (or super-heterodyne) interferometer would not provide advantages over the applied homodyne setup, especially with regard to spectral resolution. A significant disadvantage represents the need of a second often frequency-stabilized laser.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that both methods can be adapted to other types of modulation (i.e., sinusoidal) and applied for the analysis of spectra recorded by wavelength modulation spectroscopy (D. Viveiros et al., 2014).

Note: This **Chapter 4** was published in *Bahr and Wolff, 2021*.

Chapter 5

PAS-based Isotopologic Analysis of Highly Concentrated Methane

Based on the knowledge gained in [Chapter 3](#) regarding the optimal wavelength for TDLS analysis and the spectral behavior of an ICL in injection-current modulation mode investigated in [Chapter 4](#), the development of a PAS-based measurement setup for isotopologue detection of highly concentrated methane can now be presented.

In this Chapter, measurements of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ mixtures in nitrogen with concentrations of 25–70% and 0.28–3.00%, respectively, under laboratory conditions, are presented. The measurement results are then evaluated using cross-validation in conjunction with Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR). This process is also used for sensor calibration. [Section 5.2](#) shows the relevant methane absorption spectra and describes the experimental setup and the measurement procedure. [Section 5.3](#) presents the resulting measurements, which are subsequently discussed in [Section 5.4](#).

In the following, the fundamentals of photoacoustic spectroscopy are described.

5.1 Photoacoustic Spectroscopy

Photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS) is based on the photoacoustic effect discovered by Alexander Graham Bell in 1880 and is nowadays an established optical method for the determination of trace gas concentrations (Bell, 1880). With the help of this method, one molecule of interest can be detected in a billion or more foreign molecules (Palzer, 2020). This facilitates the PAS-based identification of analytes with detection limits in the ppb range or lower. The photoacoustic effect occurs in gases as well as in liquids and in solids. As can be deduced from the term photoacoustic, the effect is based on light (photo) and sound (acoustic). Accordingly, light energy is converted into sound energy. When light of a specific wavelength is absorbed by a gas molecule, the molecule changes to the excited state. As a consequence of relaxation processes, the change back to a lower-energy state of the molecule occurs either radiatively, i.e. by emitting a photon, or non-radiatively. These processes, which contribute to the formation of the photoacoustic signal, are based on the transfer of the internal energy (mainly vibrational energy, but also rotational energy) of the excited molecules into kinetic energy (translational energy) through inelastic collisions with neighboring molecules (Schilt et al., 2006). According to the kinetic theory of gases, the increase in kinetic energy is equivalent to an increase in the temperature of the gas (Giancoli, 2023). The local temperature increase provides for a pressure change according to the ideal gas law.

The change in pressure generated by a single excitation of the molecules would be too small to be detected by a microphone, for example. For this reason, modulation of the exciting laser radiation is required. The modulation frequency is selected so that it corresponds to the resonance frequency of the resonator in which the gas molecules are located. This creates a standing wave in the resonator, which can be detected by a sound transducer. The transducer

is placed in an antinode in the measuring cell where the sound pressure is at its maximum. The measurement cell used in this work is described in detail in [Section 5.2.2](#). The resonant geometry of the measuring cell typically leads to an amplification of the photoacoustic signal by a factor of 100-1,000. In addition, this amplification leads to a significant increase of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of the PA Signal, which decreases the detection limit (Miklós and Hess, 2000).

The process of photoacoustic effect is schematically shown in [Figure 5.1](#).

FIGURE 5.1: Flowchart of the photoacoustic effect.

5.1.1 Modulation Techniques

The established modulation method in PAS is modulation using a mechanical chopper. The chopper consists of a motor-driven slotted, rotating blade, which is positioned between the laser and the measuring cell and causes an "on-off" modulation of the laser radiation. This method allows to measure the photoacoustic spectrum of the analyte directly, if a continuously tunable

laser source is used. However, the limited frequency stability and mechanical noise associated with this modulation method causes stochastic deviations in the photoacoustic signal and thus reduces the accuracy in identifying the individual molecules present in the gas mixture (Germer and Wolff, 2010).

A more accurate and reproducible modulation method consists of direct modulation of the laser used. In the case of an ICL, the emitted wavelength can be tuned by changing the operating current. If the operating current is modulated sinusoidally and superimposed by a slow sweep of the mean operating current, for example, the result is wavelength modulation spectroscopy (WMS) (Wang et al., 2018). However, the application of this modulation method is not trivial, as the investigations in Chapter 4 have shown. Due to the non-linear behavior of the ICL operated in the current modulation mode, the resulting photoacoustic spectra do not correspond to the theoretical spectra. To obtain quantitative information about the analyte from the spectra, multivariate calibration based on machine learning or artificial intelligence is an appropriate approach.

5.1.2 Demodulation of the PA Signal

The photoacoustic signal is present in modulated form in the electrical signal detected by the transducer. Demodulation is required to extract the PA signal from the electrical signal. As an established method, a lock-in amplifier is used, which uses the modulation signal frequency for demodulation purpose (Burdett, 2005). The PA signal $u_{PA}(t)$ is mixed down to the baseband in parallel by a cosine and a sine oscillator, both operating at modulation frequency. In this way, the in-phase ($I(t)$) and quadrature ($Q(t)$) signals are created. Subsequently, a low-pass (LP) filter is used to suppress the high-frequency signal components, so that the PA signal results in a DC signal $u_{DC}(t)$ from

the inphase and quadrature signal branches after magnitude formation, which removes the phase deviation between $u_{PA}(t)$ and the oscillator's reference signals. The block diagram of the lock-in amplifier based demodulation is shown in [Figure 5.2](#).

FIGURE 5.2: Block diagram of lock-in amplifier based PA signal demodulation.

In the case of indirect modulation of the laser by "on-off keying", the demodulated DC signal correlates with the theoretical spectrum amplitude of the gas mixture as a function of the emitted wavelength of the laser. If the direct sinusoidal modulation of the laser injection-current is used, in case of demodulation on the modulation frequency, a $1f$ -spectrum is obtained, i.e. the recorded spectrum correlates to the derivative of the theoretical absorption spectrum.

Lock-in amplifiers exist as ready-to-use hardware components based on digital signal processing. In the context of this work the Model 7265 of the company Ametek was used.

Since the demodulation based on the lock-in amplifier corresponds to a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), the demodulation can also be implemented highly efficiently in the form of a Goertzel algorithm (Goertzel, 1958; Saalberg et al., 2017; Bruhns et al., 2018). This algorithm calculates only the required spectral component and not the entire spectrum. Since the computation of the spectrum by Goertzel algorithm is limited to a few computational operations, real-time implementations, e.g. on DSPs, are possible (Engelberg, 2008).

5.2 Methods and Materials

5.2.1 $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ Absorption Spectra

The isotopologic analysis has been performed using a spectrally tunable interband cascade laser (ICL) emitting in the spectral range of the fundamental vibration of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$. **Figure 1.1** shows the absorption spectra of the two isotopologues at room temperature (296 K) and atmospheric pressure (1,013.25 hPa) (HITRAN, 2024). The optimum center wavelength of the laser has been determined to 3,320.7 nm according **Chapter 3**. **Figure 5.3** displays the Q-branches of the fundamental vibrational absorption together with the tuning range of the laser, represented by the yellow box.

FIGURE 5.3: Q-branches of the fundamental vibrational absorption spectra of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ (Gordon et al., 2022) together with the tuning range of the ICL (yellow box).

5.2.2 Measurement Setup

The measurement setup is schematically shown in [Figure 5.4](#). The ICL 3272 used in this investigation was manufactured by nanoplus GmbH (Gerbrunn, Germany). It exhibits a center wavelength of 3,323 nm with a spectral linewidth below 3 MHz. The laser can be operated at temperatures between 20 and 30 degrees Celsius. Stimulated emission occurs with electric currents between 19 and 120 mA. The ICL is operated using the Thorlabs (Newton, MA/United States) laser diode driver TLD001 and its temperature is controlled by the Thorlabs controller TTC001. The laser current can be set with an accuracy of 10 μ A. The noise level is below 3 μ A rms. The ICL chip has been installed in a TO66 housing including a Peltier element and a temperature sensor for temperature regulation. The laser provides single-mode emission that is spectrally continuously tunable between 3,318.41 nm and 3,330.64 nm. The maximum output power is approximately 15 mW. The laser beam passes centrally through the cylindrically symmetrical photoacoustic cell. The custom-made cell is designed according to the established H geometry featuring a longitudinal resonance around 3 kHz (Nodov, 1978). The resonance tube is 60 mm long with a diameter of 6 mm and the buffer volumes at both ends of the cell have each a length of 30 mm and a diameter of 24 mm, resulting in a total absorption length of 120 mm. The material of the cell is aluminum. The windows of the cell consist of CaF₂, which provide around 93% transmission for wavelengths around 3 μ m. The photoacoustics signal is detected by the analog microphone ROM-2235P-HD-R from PUI Audio (Fairborn, OH/United States) which is mounted in the center of the cell with the membrane flush with the inner wall. It exhibits a diameter of 5.8 mm and a detection sensitivity of -35 ± 3 dB at 1 kHz and 50 cm distance. The Ametek/Signal Recovery lock-in amplifier DSP LIA 7265 (Berwyn, IL/United States) performs the phase-sensitive detection of the microphone

signal. The Owon (Zhangzhou, China) function generator AG 1022 provides the frequency reference for the ICL modulation and the lock-in detection. The entire experimental setup is controlled using a MATLAB script on a PC. The PLSR algorithm including the leave-one-out cross-validation is implemented in a MATLAB script and performed by the PC.

FIGURE 5.4: Experimental setup.

The gas flow system is schematically shown in Figure 5.5. Gas is provided in three containers:

1. CH_4 of natural isotopologue abundance (1 L geometric volume, 12 bar filling pressure, purity: 4.5, distributor: Westfalen AG),
2. $^{13}CH_4$ (416 ml geometric volume, 2.3 bar filling pressure, purity: 99%, distributor: Merck/Sigma Aldrich),
3. N_2 (10 L geometric volume, 200 bar filling pressure, purity: 5.0, distributor: Westfalen AG).

FIGURE 5.5: Gas flow system.

Mixtures are generated using the 6 Channel Gas mixer from QCAL (Munich, Germany) which is controlled by a PC. The maximum relative error of the mixture concentrations, specified by the manufacturer, is up to 2%. To ensure the correctness of the mixer performance, all compositions are analyzed by the gas chromatograph 9130 from Fisons (Ipswich, United Kingdom). The photoacoustic measurements were performed under static conditions after the gas mixtures were injected into the gas cell.

5.2.3 Measurement Procedure

Photoacoustic spectroscopy is based on the absorption of modulated radiation and the subsequent conversion of the absorbed energy by collisions into a thermal wave and consequently into a pressure wave. This sound wave can be amplified taking advantage of an acoustic resonance of the sample cell and is usually detected by a microphone (Demtröder, 2014a; Demtröder, 2014b).

The ICL applied in this investigation is directly injection-current modulated at a constant operation temperature of 20 degrees Celsius. The current consists of one part that is continuously tuned between 75 and 120 mA covering a

spectral range of approximately 12 nm and a second, sinusoidally modulated part that is responsible for the generation of the PA signal. The latter exhibits a modulation amplitude of 1.24 mA which corresponds to a spectral range of approximately 0.1 nm.

The frequency of the reference signal fed into the lock-in amplifier equals the resonance frequency of the measurement cell. This leads to a $1f$ wavelength modulation, as a result of which the recorded spectra correspond to the derivative of the absorption spectra. The advantage of this modulation method is that changes in the spectra are emphasized. This makes it easier to distinguish different gas components.

The acoustic resonance of a sample cell depends sensitively on the speed of sound. Due to the significant mass difference, doubling or tripling a methane concentration of 25% in an N_2 matrix considerably changes the speed of sound resulting in a large shift of the cell's resonance frequency (Selvaraj et al., 2019). **Figure 5.6** illustrates this phenomenon. It shows the PA signal as function of the modulation frequency for (total) methane concentrations of 26.25%, 52.25%, 73.00% and 100.00%. Shifts in the resonant frequency due to temperature fluctuations of a few degrees Celsius are negligible, since the resonant frequency dependency can be described by $\frac{f_1}{f_2} = \sqrt{\frac{T_1}{T_2}}$, where f_x stands for the resonant frequency corresponding to the gas temperature T_x inside the resonator. The subsequent analytical measurements were all performed at a modulation frequency of 3,187 Hz.

Over a large range, the PA signal is proportional to the concentration of the absorbing molecules. However, if the absorption is extremely strong, as in the case of the fundamental asymmetric stretching ν_3 of methane, and/or the concentration of the absorbing species is very high, saturation occurs

and deviations from this linear relationship arise (Menduni et al., 2022). In **Figure 5.6** it can be observed that the PA signal at the respective resonance frequency decreases as the methane concentration increases from 26.25% to 100.00%. The reason for this is twofold. Firstly, the majority of the absorption takes place in an increasingly shorter path length behind the entrance window. As a consequence, the overlap between the longitudinal mode and the intensity distribution of the laser will be weaker and the cell resonance is stimulated less effectively (Baumann et al., 2006; Baumann et al., 2007). The linear dependency between concentration and photoacoustic signal that applies in the ppm and ppb range is then no longer observable. For methane concentrations in the single digit percentage level the photoacoustic signal still increases with increasing concentration, however the dependence is non-linear (Zeninari et al., 2016). If concentrations are in the high percentage range, as shown in **Figure 5.6**, there is a reduction in amplitude with further increasing concentration.

FIGURE 5.6: Photoacoustics signal as function of the modulation frequency for different mixtures.

This phenomenon is superimposed by a second effect. The photoacoustic signal generation is based on the transfer of internal energy of excited molecules (mainly vibration but also rotation) into kinetic energy of neighboring molecules (translation) via inelastic collisions. Therefore, the composition of the gas matrix significantly affects the relaxation dynamics and thus the photoacoustic response. Due to the high purity of the gas samples, the controlled laboratory environment and the evacuable gas flow system it is not expected that water vapor or other impurities play a major role in the relaxation process. Since there are no significant differences between the relaxation times of the two methane isotopologues, the $^{12}\text{CH}_4/^{13}\text{CH}_4$ ratio should also not have a substantial influence on the photoacoustic signal (Giglio et al., 2022). As no efficient vibro-vibrational (V-V) transition between the ν_3 state of CH_4 (CH_4^*) and N_2 exists, only three non-radiative relaxation channels are possible (Schilt et al., 2006):

1. CH_4^*-N_2 collision followed by a vibro-translational (V-T) transition. This relaxation channel represents the main source of the PA signal if N_2 is present in the mixture.
2. $\text{CH}_4^*-\text{CH}_4$ collision followed by V-V transitions. This relaxation channel does not contribute to the PA signal.
3. $\text{CH}_4^*-\text{CH}_4$ collisions followed by a V-T transition. This relaxation channel represents an additional source of the PA signal. The respective signal is phase-shifted in relation to the CH_4^*-N_2 signal. If no N_2 is present in the mixture, it is the only source of the PA signal.

In the analytical measurements the (total) methane concentrations are varied between 25.28 and 73%. This changes the number of nitrogen molecules available for the according V-T collisions considerably and thus determines the efficiency of the photoacoustic signal generation.

The evaluation algorithm responsible for the sensor calibration has to be able to compensate the changing dependencies originating from the effectivity of the acoustic resonance stimulation as well as the matrix effects arising from changes in the gas composition.

5.3 Results

Table 5.1 lists the nine isotopologue mixtures that were investigated. The residual gas to 100% was always N_2 . The $^{12}CH_4$ concentrations were chosen to cover the two-digit percentage range as complete as possible. The choice of $^{13}CH_4$ concentrations was severely restricted due to the flow limitations of the gas mixer. **Figure 5.7** to **Figure 5.9** show the respective photoacoustic spectra, i.e. the PA signal as function of the average laser current. All measurements were taken at a sample temperature of 26 degrees Celsius and a pressure of 1,016 hPa.

TABLE 5.1: $^{12}CH_4$ and $^{13}CH_4$ concentrations of the nine investigated mixtures (rest: N_2).

Mixture No.	Figure No.	$^{12}CH_4$ concentration	$^{13}CH_4$ concentration
1			- 0.28%
2	Figure 5.7	25%	- 0.75%
3			- 1.25%
4			- 0.56%
5	Figure 5.8	50%	- 1.75%
6			- 2.25%
7			- 0.78%
8	Figure 5.9	70%	- 2.25%
9			- 3.00%

FIGURE 5.7: Photoacoustic signal as function of the average laser current for 25% $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ with three different $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ shares in nitrogen.

FIGURE 5.8: Photoacoustic signal as function of the average laser current for 50% $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ with three different $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ shares in nitrogen.

FIGURE 5.9: Photoacoustic signal as function of the average laser current for 70% $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ with three different $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ shares in nitrogen.

Considering the complexity of the collected spectra a sensor calibration in the form of a quantitative multivariate approach is implemented to validate the methane isotopologue concentrations and to test the suitability of the method. In particular, Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) proved to be applicable for determining the concentrations of mixture components from photoacoustic spectra (Loh and Wolff, 2020; Saalberg and Wolff, 2018). Figure 5.10 shows the true and the predicted methane isotopologue concentrations, after a leave-one-out cross-validation based on PLSR was applied to all nine investigated mixtures. The mixture numbers in Figure 5.10 correspond to the order given in Table 5.1. The absolute root-mean-square-errors for the predicted $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ concentrations were calculated to 3.08% and 0.29%, respectively.

FIGURE 5.10: Evaluation of the investigated methane isotopologue mixtures by leave-one-out cross-validation based on PLSR.

5.4 Discussion

Figures 5.7 to 5.9 show wavelength-modulated photoacoustic spectra that were measured using the single modulation frequency ($1f$) as reference for the lock-in amplification. Therefore, they represent approximately the derivative of the absorption spectrum (Demtröder, 2014a; Demtröder, 2014b). However, due to the nonlinear spectral behavior of injection current modulated semiconductor lasers, as investigated in Chapter 4, the agreement is not perfect. In addition, the spectra are not normalized with respect to the emission power of the laser and the output depends considerably on the modulation amplitude.

The spectral tuning range of the laser was selected using an optimization algorithm in such a way that not only characteristic absorption lines of both isotopologues are accessible, but that these lines also have absorption strengths

of the same order of magnitude around the isotopologue ratio of interest (natural abundance). The latter is important as it ensures that the signal levels are comparable.

The spectral region associated with average laser currents between 75 mA and 85 mA is clearly dominated by $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ lines. This is illustrated by the fact that the according peaks are only weakly dependent on the $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ concentration. However, the dependence of the photoacoustic signal on the $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ concentration is significant. The spectral region associated with average laser currents between 85 mA and 120 mA, on the other hand, is obviously characterized by $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ absorption. However, $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ exhibits a considerable contribution in this range leading to a base-signal that increases with increasing $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ concentration. The $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ concentration dependent signal inversion, which is for instance observable between 25% and 50% $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ around 103 mA, marked by yellow boxes, can be explained as a result of two opposing effects:

1. Increasing signal with increasing concentration due to higher absorption.
2. Decreasing signal with increasing concentration due to less effective stimulation of cell resonance (see [Section 5.2.3](#)).

The inversion can only be observed at selected average laser currents because the phenomenon requires a specific combination of absorption path length, absorption coefficient and concentration, in which the contributions of the two isotopologues add up.

In conclusion it can be stated that, even though the number of investigated mixtures of the two main methane isotopologues $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ is, with nine samples, quite limited and the error of the gas mixer used is significant, the measurements displayed in [Figures 5.7 to 5.9](#) and the evaluation based on PLSR displayed in [Figure 5.10](#) prove to a satisfactory extent that photoacoustic

spectroscopy is a suitable method for the isotopologic analysis of highly concentrated methane. The accuracy of the sensor can be considerably improved by adding more measurements to the training data of the PLSR algorithm. The presented results with samples in the high double-digit percentage range make it appear possible to analyze undiluted natural gas samples. However, the presence of other hydrocarbons would make this task significantly more challenging. In any case, it is important to consider the resonance frequency shift associated with concentration changes.

Note: Parts of this **Chapter 5** were published in *Bahr and Wolff, 2022*.

Chapter 6

Analysis of Natural Gas Samples using PAS

While in [Chapter 5](#) only artificial mixtures of methane main isotopologues were measured using PAS, in this chapter real natural gas samples are investigated. In the following, a photoacoustic analyzer that can determine the concentrations of methane, ethane and propane of real natural gas samples is described. The sensor is a further development of the setup described in [Chapter 5](#). The investigated natural gas originates from the house supply of Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (Hamburg, Germany). Furthermore, gas samples originating from a German natural gas storage are investigated. In this regard, a method for preparing gas samples of atmospheric pressure for the photoacoustic measurement is presented. The investigation of natural gas-like compositions and real natural gas samples were carried out in the methane, ethane and propane concentration range of 7-87%, 4-5% and 0.5-1.0%, respectively.

6.1 Methods and Material

6.1.1 Methane, Ethane and Propane Absorption Spectra

The analyzer is based on an interband cascade laser (ICL) emitting in the mid-infrared range. **Figure 6.1** shows the normalized absorption spectra of methane, ethane and propane at room temperature (296 K) and atmospheric pressure (1013.25 hPa). The center wavelength of the laser has been empirically selected to be 3324.15 nm and is displayed by the vertical dark line in the yellow box in **Figure 6.2**. To clearly identify several components of a gas mixture, it is necessary to analyze the spectrum in a specific range. For this purpose, the laser is spectrally tuned. The yellow box represents the laser tuning range whose spectral bandwidth is approximately 5.3 nm.

FIGURE 6.1: Absorption spectra of methane, ethane and propane (GEISA, 2022; Gordon et al., 2022).

FIGURE 6.2: Absorption spectra of methane, ethane and propane together with the laser tuning range (yellow box) and the laser center wavelength (GEISA, 2022; Gordon et al., 2022).

6.1.2 Measurement Setup

The measurement setup is schematically shown in [Figure 6.3](#). The ICL 3272 manufactured by nanoplus GmbH (Gerbrunn, Germany) emits radiation around 3323 nm with a spectral linewidth smaller than 3 MHz. The laser chip temperature can be varied between 20 and 30 degrees Celsius. Laser operating currents between 19 and 120 mA allow stimulated emission. For the operation of the ICL the Thorlabs (Newton, MA/USA) laser diode driver TLD001 and the temperature controller TTC001 are used. The TLD001 allows to set the laser current with an accuracy of 10 μA with a noise level below 3 μA rms. Installed in a TO66 housing, the ICL chip temperature is controlled using a temperature sensor and a Peltier element. The single-mode emission can be continuously tuned between 3318.41 nm and 3330.64 nm. Approximately 25 mW output power can be reached at maximum. The cylindrically

symmetrical photoacoustic measurement cell, that the laser beam centrally passes, is designed according to the established H geometry, as described in [Section 5.2.2](#), featuring a longitudinal resonance around 3 kHz (Nodov, 1978). The photoacoustic signal is detected with the analog microphone ROM-2235P-HD-R from PUI Audio (Fairborn, OH/USA) which is mounted in the center of the cell, membrane flush with the wall. The microphone exhibits a diameter of 5.8 mm and a detection sensitivity of -35 ± 3 dB at 1 kHz and 50 cm distance. The temperature of the measurement cell is controlled by the A-senco (Aalen, Germany) temperature controller, which heats the cell to a constant temperature above the ambient temperature by means of two heating mats. The accuracy of the temperature control could be determined to ± 0.1 degrees Celsius. The maximum heating power is 30 W. The demodulation is performed on a Texas Instruments (Dallas, TX/USA) TMS320C6713 digital signal processor (DSP) which is mounted on the Texas Instruments TMDSDSK6713 evaluation board. The laser current modulation is controlled by the digital signal processor as well. A PC is used to control laser diode driver, TEC controller and DSP. The photoacoustic signals calculated by the DSP are recorded by the PC as function of the average current. These spectra of known mixtures serve as basis for a PLSR model based on a MATLAB script, which can subsequently be used to calculate the concentrations of the single components of unknown mixtures.

FIGURE 6.3: Experimental setup.

The gas flow system for the generation of the calibration mixtures is schematically shown in [Figure 6.4](#). The gas is provided in four containers:

- CH_4 : 10 L geometric volume, 200 bar filling pressure, purity: 2.5, distributor: Westfalen AG,
- C_2H_6 : 1 L geometric volume, 12 bar filling pressure, purity: 2.0, distributor: Westfalen AG,
- C_3H_8 : 1 L geometric volume, 7.3 bar filling pressure, purity: 2.5, distributor: Westfalen AG,
- N_2 : 10 L geometric volume, 200 bar filling pressure, purity: 5.0, distributor: Westfalen AG.

All gas mixtures for calibration are generated using the 4-channel gas mixer based on Vögtlin Instruments GmbH (MuttENZ, Swiss) mass flow controllers (MFC), which are distributed by HTK Hamburg GmbH (Hamburg, Germany). The maximum relative error of a single MFC is specified to be up to 1%.

FIGURE 6.4: Gas flow system.

The validation measurements of the natural gas samples were carried out using the Shimadzu (Kyōto, Japan) GC 2014, which is equipped with an FID and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). The relative measurement error is specified to be up to 2%.

The storage gas sample was provided by GEO-data (Garbsen, Germany) in a gas collection tube with a geometric volume of about 350 ml. The storage gas originates from a natural gas storage facility within Germany. Its preparation has been performed using the setup shown in [Figure 6.5](#). A lecture bottle (geometric volume approximately 400 ml) was evacuated by the VACUUBRAND GmbH & Co. KG (Wertheim, Germany) Chemistry-HYBRID pump down to 0.1 mbar absolute pressure.

FIGURE 6.5: Storage gas preparation system.

The natural gas samples used are from Hamburger Energiewerke GmbH (Hamburg, Germany) and were obtained from the house gas connection of the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences.

6.1.3 Measurement Procedure

At a constant temperature of 20 degrees Celsius, the ICL applied in this investigation is operated in the injection-current modulation mode. The injection-current consists of two parts. One part is continuously tuned between 66.00 and 120.12 mA covering a spectral range of approximately 5.3 nm. The other part is sinusoidally modulated with an amplitude of 1.18 mA which corresponds to a spectral range of approximately 0.1 nm.

The temperature of the measurement cell is set and controlled to constant 30 degrees C by the temperature controller.

The microphone signal is sampled at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz. The recorded spectra consist of 315 points, with each spectral component calculated from 1,500 samples. The demodulation of the microphone signal on the DSP, based on the Goertzel algorithm, is performed at the injection-current modulation frequency at 3,528 Hz (Engelberg, 2008). The resulting spectra correspond

approximately to the first derivative of the absorption spectra, which emphasizes the changes in the absorption coefficient, induced by changes in the single gas concentrations.

Figure 6.6 shows exemplary photoacoustic spectra, i.e. the PA signals as function of the average laser current after the Goertzel algorithm based demodulation on the DSP. All measurements were taken at a sample (cell) temperature of 30 degrees C and a pressure of 1,013 hPa.

FIGURE 6.6: Exemplary photoacoustic spectra of natural gas and storage gas measured on 28th June 2023 and 29th June 2023, respectively.

The investigation of complex gas mixtures such as natural gas requires a multivariate approach to determine the methane, ethane and propane shares. As shown in previous investigations, Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) proved to be suitable for this task (Menduni et al., 2022). Reference calibration measurements of the photoacoustic sensor are required to predict the individual shares of the natural gas samples with a high precision and reliability.

A training data set of 20 different mixtures has been used, all concentrations are uniform distributed. All calibration gas mixtures consist of methane, ethane and propane. The calculation of the PLSR model is performed on the PC. The magnitudes of the spectrum represent the predictor scores and the corresponding known concentrations provide the response scores. The beta-parameters are the result of the PLSR model calculation, which are the basis for the prediction of gas mixture compositions. By multiplication and summation operations of the beta-parameters with the spectra of unknown mixtures, the concentrations of its hydrocarbon components are calculated (Rosipal and Krämer, 2006).

A complete measurement run including calculation of the unknown hydrocarbon concentrations of a gas mixture requires approximately 12 seconds.

The filling and purging of the measuring cell are carried out as shown in [Figure 6.4](#) using gas samples with overpressure relative to the atmosphere. If the gas samples do not have an overpressure, they must be prepared according to [Figure 6.5](#). In this case, a lecture bottle is evacuated. The pressure in the system is less than 0.5 mbar when evacuated. The valve of the gas collection tube is subsequently opened and a constant pressure lower than the ambient pressure is established in the system. To generate the necessary overpressure relative to the atmosphere, the lecture bottle is then filled with nitrogen up to 4 bar above atmospheric pressure. This procedure allows a sample preparation adequate for the measurement cell. The concentration ratios of the single hydrocarbons, except for nitrogen, remain unchanged.

For GC analysis, the samples are injected into the GC by means of a dosing loop which, in conjunction with a valve circuit, dispenses the analyte onto the packed column. After 12 minutes retention time the measuring results of the TCD and the FID are available. The evaluation of the chromatograms is based on calibration curves, which were measured using the following calibration gases:

- Methane: 2.5%, 50%, 100%
- Ethane: 0.85%, 1%, 100%
- Propane: 0.85%, 100%
- Nitrogen: 100%

The residual gases are in all cases nitrogen.

6.2 Results

Table 6.1 lists all gas samples that were investigated. The natural gas samples of the supplier Hamburger Energiewerke GmbH have been investigated at three different times. Due to the ambient pressure of the storage gas sample, it had to be prepared and diluted as described in **Section 6.1.2** using the setup shown in **Figure 6.5**. PAS did not detect any propane in this sample and the GC result was “less than 1‰”.

Figures 6.7 and **6.8** show the true and the predicted shares for methane and ethane exemplarily. The absolute root mean square errors (RMSE) for the methane, ethane and propane concentrations in **Figure 6.7** are 1.34%, 0.19% and 0.13%, respectively. The absolute RMSE for methane and ethane concentrations in **Figure 6.8** are 0.29% and 0.03%, respectively.

TABLE 6.1: Analysis results.

Sample type	Date	PAS			GC		
		Methane	Ethane	Propane	Methane	Ethane	Propane
Natural gas	26 th May 2023	86.11%	4.98%	0.92%	85.23%	4.70%	0.96%
	28 th June 2023	85.03%	4.95%	0.67%	85.10%	4.96%	0.87%
	2 nd August 2023	82.35%	4.60%	0.62%	84.33%	4.41%	0.77%
Storage gas	29 th June 2023	6.79%	0.41%	-	6.78%	0.48%	<0.1%

FIGURE 6.7: Results of the leave-one-out cross-validation of natural gas (propane is hidden for clarity).

FIGURE 6.8: Results of the leave-one-out cross-validation of storage gas.

The number of training data sets significantly influences the absolute RMSE.

Figure 6.9 illustrates this relationship.

FIGURE 6.9: Absolute RMSE as function of the number of training data sets.

Figures 6.10 and 6.11 show boxplots of natural gas and storage measurements, respectively, using PAS.

FIGURE 6.10: Boxplots of natural gas PAS measurements on 2nd August 2023.

FIGURE 6.11: Boxplots of storage gas PAS measurements on 29th June 2023.

6.3 Discussion

Figure 6.6 shows an exemplary photoacoustic spectrum. It does not perfectly correspond to the derivative of the absorption spectrum, due to the nonlinear spectral behavior of the injection-current modulation and the missing normalization regarding the laser output power.

As shown in Table 6.1, the PAS results are in good agreement with the GC results. If we consider that the GC exhibits a relative error of up to 2%, the agreement can be described as excellent.

The boxplots in Figures 6.10 and 6.11 show the respective median of the measured values represented by the horizontal red bars. The upper and lower horizontal blue edges of the box show the 75% and 25% percentiles respectively and the whiskers the maximum and minimum measured values for each individual natural gas component. According to the values displayed in Figures 6.10 and 6.11, the precision can be considered satisfactory.

As displayed in Figure 6.9, an increase of the number of training data sets leads to a significantly decreasing absolute RMSE. Although only a relatively low number of 20 training data sets were used for this investigation, accurate

results could be achieved. The accuracy is given, as there is sufficient agreement with the GC measured values regarded as reference.

A further increase of the number of training data sets would further decrease the error. The PLSR algorithm used is a mathematical algorithm that is based on the principal component analysis of the predictor variables as well as the response variables and links the values generated by the principal component analyses via the covariance. The resulting mathematical construct is therefore transparent and can be assigned to explainable artificial intelligence. The accuracy as well as the precision of the predictions by PLSR depend mainly on the quality of the measured spectra. The prediction error is therefore mainly dependent on the configuration of the parameters of the measurement setup, especially the design of the digital signal processing stage. The error can therefore be reduced to a low value by selecting optimal parameters within the signal processing. As the main source of error is not attributable to the PLSR algorithm, it is therefore hardly possible to draw conclusions about the dependency of the error from analyzing the PLSR internal values. A direct statistical analysis of the recorded spectra appears to be more effective at this point with regard to the expected error.

The natural gas analysis on 28th June 2023 delivered a methane concentration of 85.03% (PAS) and 85.10% (GC), respectively (see [Table 6.1](#)). Both values do not agree with the 91.95% officially published by Gasnetz Hamburg GmbH (Hamburg, Germany) for this month (Gasnetz Hamburg GmbH, [2023](#)). The true value is almost 7% smaller.

Optimal operating parameters of gas-fired devices depend on composition because methane, ethane and propane require different amounts of oxygen for a complete combustion (Demoulin et al., [2008](#)). If the ratio of oxygen to gas components is not correct, incomplete combustion can occur, reducing energy efficiency and potentially causing harmful emissions. The knowledge of the composition helps to set the right combustion conditions to ensure optimal

and environmentally friendly combustion (Wei et al., 2021).

In addition, the composition of natural gas has a significant influence on the monetary value of the natural gas. Both industrial and private customers of natural gas receive bills based on average values of the natural gas composition and thus the energy content. Knowing the actual composition of the natural gas purchased would make it possible to create correct bills regarding the energy content.

With the help of the PAS-based sensor described in this **Chapter 6** the therefore necessary monitoring of the natural gas composition could be performed at the customer site.

In conclusion it can be stated that, photoacoustic spectroscopy in combination with PLSR is a suitable method for analyzing natural gas samples as well as storage gas samples in a wide dynamic range. Due to the short analysis time of approximately 12 seconds and the absence of any operating gases, the presented PAS-based sensor could be further developed into an alternative to GC that is attractive in terms of price and performance.

Note: Parts of this **Chapter 6** were published in *Bahr and Wolff, 2023*.

Chapter 7

Summary and Outlook

The overall goal of this research is the development of a measurement setup and procedure based on photoacoustic spectroscopy which is used to quantitatively analyze the composition of natural gas and the main methane isotopologues $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ of natural gas-like mixtures.

Natural gas is one of the most important energy sources of our time, and its composition provides information about its energy content and origin. The composition of the main methane isotopologues can be used to derive further information regarding the degree of maturity of the natural gas as well as to optimize the extraction technology.

There are a variety of methods for analyzing natural gas. Gas chromatography is considered the gold standard in natural gas analysis. This enables analyses from ppb to the percentage range per component of the natural gas, with deviations of less than 2%. The extension of a gas chromatograph by isotope ratio mass spectroscopy enables the detection of the $^{13}\text{CH}_4/^{12}\text{CH}_4$ isotopologue ratio. The main disadvantages are the need for at least one operating gas, laboratory conditions to produce reproducible results, continuous calibrations to compensate for detector drift and the lack of compactness of the gas chromatograph and isotope ratio mass spectrometer. In-situ measurements are therefore hardly possible.

Furthermore, there are a number of spectroscopic methods, which are, however, also rarely suitable for field measurements due to construction-related reasons.

The choice of the optimal laser wavelength is crucial for the success of spectroscopic measurements. Since the spectra of the main alkanes partly overlap strongly, it is hardly possible to determine the optimum wavelength range empirically. Therefore, a mathematical algorithm is presented in this thesis, which enables the calculation of the optimal wavelength, based on the theoretical absorption spectra, for the detection of the main alkanes and the main methane isotopologues. For the latter, an average wavelength of 3,320.7 nm is obtained.

Photoacoustic spectroscopy requires the modulation of laser radiation. To achieve precise results, the exact knowledge of the spectral behavior of the laser used is prerequisite. The modulation can be performed indirectly, e.g. with the aid of a "chopper", or directly by modulating the laser injection-current or the laser temperature. The direct modulation of the laser leads to maximum reproducibility of the measurements and at the same time poses a challenge, as there is still no commercially available measuring device to analyze the spectral behavior of an interband cascade laser modulated in the kHz range with high wavelength resolution.

For this reason, a Michelson interferometer-based method is presented in this thesis, which uses a reference wavelength, determined by transmission spectroscopy, to determine the absolute emitted wavelength as a function of the laser operating current with sawtooth modulation in the frequency range from 10 Hz to 30 kHz. It can be seen that the dynamic range with respect to the wavelength of the interband cascade laser used decreases with increasing modulation frequency.

The analysis of the spectral behavior of the analyzed interband cascade laser shows that it can be used directly modulated in photoacoustic spectroscopy and is therefore suitable for natural gas and main methane isotopologue analysis.

The analysis of the main methane isotopologues $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ poses a major challenge due to their strongly overlapping absorption spectra. Thus, an interband cascade laser is used to differentiate the two molecules. This laser emits single-mode with a spectral bandwidth of less than 3 MHz, which enables high-resolution spectroscopy and identification of the main methane isotopologue concentrations.

The main isotopologue mixture to be analyzed is located in a measuring cell in which an analog electret microphone is also integrated. To minimize negative temperature influences on the measurements, the temperature of the measuring cell is controlled. The methane molecules are excited by the injection-current modulated interband cascade laser and the resulting photoacoustic signal is converted into an electrical signal by an analog microphone. A lock-in amplifier is used to demodulate the photoacoustic signal, resulting in a spectrum dependent on the laser operating current. Spectra are measured for various main methane isotopologue mixtures, resulting in training data sets for the Partial Least Squares Regression model. With the help of this machine-learning-based model, spectra of unknown main methane isotopologue mixtures can be analyzed quantitatively with regard to the concentrations of the individual main methane isotopologues.

Synthetic $^{13}\text{CH}_4/^{12}\text{CH}_4$ mixtures in nitrogen with concentrations of 0.28–3.00% and 25–70%, respectively, under laboratory conditions, are investigated. The absolute root-mean-square-errors for the predicted $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ concentrations are calculated to 3.08% and 0.29%, respectively.

The sensor thus appears to be suitable for analyzing natural gas-like methane

main isotopologue concentrations.

Finally, the photoacoustic sensor is evaluated in natural gas analysis with the aim of analyzing real natural gas samples with regard to the main alkanes methane, ethane and propane. To this end, the sensor is calibrated using synthetic mixtures similar to natural gas, which simulate various main alkane compositions.

The analysis of three natural gas samples from the Hamburg gas network shows that the sensor exhibits only minor deviations compared to the gas chromatography analysis carried out in parallel and is therefore able to analyze real natural gas samples in real-time with a measurement time of approximately 12 seconds.

In addition, a method is presented that allows the preparation of natural gas samples under atmospheric pressure so that they are subsequently pressurized and can thus be analyzed with the photoacoustic sensor. This method is applied to a storage gas sample, which is then analyzed with the photoacoustic sensor described. It is shown that even in the single-digit percentage range of the main alkane concentrations, very good results are achieved in comparison to the gas chromatography analysis.

It has been shown that the sensor is able to analyze both main methane isotopologues and real natural gas samples with regard to the individual concentrations of their components with sufficient accuracy. The sensor has so far only been tested on a limited number of selected real natural gas samples. It is currently not possible to say to what extent the sensor works reliably with highly contaminated samples, such as those found in the production of natural gas. An increase in precision can be achieved primarily by increasing the measurement duration. Depending on the application, it is therefore possible to achieve an optimum ratio between measurement duration and

precision. In contrast to the gold standard gas chromatography, there is a significant advantage in terms of cost, portability and measurement time. One of the next steps would be to mobilize the sensor so that the extent to which it can be used for field measurements can be investigated.

Furthermore, a performance comparison using an equivalent quartz enhanced photoacoustic spectroscopy sensor would be useful to carry out the strength and weaknesses of the use of a quartz tuning fork instead of an analog microphone.

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